

Review Article – Published in Brain Behavior & Evolution

Medina, L., Abellán, A., Morales, L., Pross, A., Metwalli, A. H., González-Alonso, A., Freixes, J., & Desfilis, E. (2023). Evolution and Development of Amygdala Subdivisions: Pallial, Subpallial, and Beyond. *Brain, behavior and evolution*, 98(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000527512>

Evolution and development of amygdala subdivisions: pallial, subpallial and beyond

Loreta Medina^{a,b}, Antonio Abellán^{a,b}, Lorena Morales^{a,b}, Alessandra Pross^b, Alek H. Metwalli^{a,b}, Alba González-Alonso^{a,b}, Júlia Freixes^a, and Ester Desfilis^{a,b}

^a Department of Experimental Medicine, University of Lleida, Lleida, Catalonia, Spain

^b Laboratory of Evolutionary and Developmental Neurobiology, Lleida's Institute for Biomedical Research – Dr. Pifarré Foundation (IRBLleida), Lleida, Catalonia, Spain

Short Title: amygdala evolution and development

Corresponding Author:

Loreta Medina, Department of Experimental Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Lleida
Avinguda Alcalde Rovira Roure 80, Lleida, Catalonia, 25198, Spain

Tel: +34 - 973702413

E-mail: loreta.medina@udl.cat

Number of Tables: 1

Number of Figures: 1

Word count: 10121

Keywords: forebrain, telencephalon, dorsal ventricular ridge, bed nucleus of the stria terminalis, birds, reptiles.

Abstract

The amygdala is a central node in functional networks regulating emotions, social behavior and social cognition. It develops in the telencephalon and includes pallial and subpallial parts, but these are extremely complex with multiple subdivisions, cell types and connections. The homology of the amygdala in non-mammals is highly controversial, especially for the pallial part, and we are still far from understanding general principles on its organization that are common to different groups. Here we review data on the adult functional architecture and developmental genoarchitecture of the amygdala in different amniotes (mammals and sauropsids), which are helping to disentangle and to better understand this complex structure. The use of an evolutionary developmental biology (evodevo) approach has helped to distinguish three major divisions in the amygdala, derived from the pallium, the subpallium and from a newly identified division called telencephalon-opto-hypothalamic domain (TOH). This approach has also helped to identify homologous cell populations with identical embryonic origins and molecular profiles in the amygdala of different amniotes. While subpallial cells produce different subtypes of GABAergic neurons, the pallium and TOH are major sources of glutamatergic cells. Available data point to a development-based molecular code that contributes to shape distinct functional subsystems in the amygdala, and comparative genoarchitecture is helping to delineate the cells involved in same subsystems in non-mammals. Thus, the evodevo approach can provide crucial information to understand common organizing principles of the amygdalar cells and networks that control behavior, emotions and cognition in amniotes.

Introduction

The amygdala is a key telencephalic structure for control of emotions, social behavior and social cognition [Phelps and LeDoux, 2005; Martínez-García et al., 2007; Medina et al., 2017]. Studies in mammals show that it is relatively small when compared to the neocortex or the striatum. However, it is widely connected with other brain areas, and is able to influence how the rest of the brain works on the basis of emotions [Todd and Anderson, 2009]. By way of connections with the hippocampus, it modulates hippocampal-dependent memories, while through connections with the striatum it appears to modulate striatal-dependent memories, reward and motivated behaviors [reviewed by Phelps and LeDoux, 2005; Medina et al., 2017]. Furthermore, through its ample direct and indirect connections with the neocortex, it also appears to modulate cortical function and facilitate attention and perception of salient, emotionally-relevant stimuli [reviewed by Phelps and LeDoux, 2005; Medina et al., 2017]. In addition, the amygdala is involved in emotional responses to social stimuli, being involved in social fear, but has also been shown to play a critical role in social recognition, affiliation, sexual and agonistic behaviors [DeVries and Miller, 1998; Swanson, 2000; Choi et al., 2005; Donaldson and Young, 2008], being part of a network related to producing adaptive social interactions [Phelps and LeDoux, 2005; Medina et al., 2019].

Studies in mammals also show that the amygdala is highly complex in terms of divisions and subdivisions, cell types and connections [Swanson and Petrovich, 1998; Martínez-García et al., 2007; Medina et al., 2017]. It is usually conceptualized as containing two major divisions, named the pallial and the subpallial amygdala. The pallial amygdala includes the basal amygdalar complex and the cortical amygdalar areas, is rich in glutamatergic neurons and shows extensive reciprocal connections with other parts of the pallium, including the cerebral cortex and the hippocampal complex [Alheid et al., 1995; Swanson and Petrovich, 1998; Medina et al., 2017]. The subpallial amygdala contains the

central and medial amygdalar nuclei and the intercalated amygdalar cells, and is rich in different subtypes of GABAergic neurons [Alheid et al., 1995; Swanson and Petrovich, 1998; Medina et al., 2017]. The subpallial amygdala receives direct or indirect inputs from the pallial amygdala and some cortical areas, and gives rise to long descending projections to the hypothalamus and brainstem, being thus able to regulate the hypothalamo-pituitary-glandular axes, the autonomic nervous system and the somatomotor system to coordinate different behavioral responses [Phelps and LeDoux, 2005; Ulrich-Lai and Herman, 2009].

The subpallial amygdala is rostromedially continuous with the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BST), and all together form the so-called centromedial extended amygdala [Alheid and Heimer, 1988; Alheid et al., 1995; de Olmos and Heimer, 1999; Heimer, 2003]. The centromedial amygdala and the BST contain similar subtypes of neurons (i.e. both include subsets of GABAergic neurons with similar neuropeptidergic content), and are reciprocally connected and engaged in the same functional pathways. Thus, the descending projections of the centromedial amygdala to the hypothalamus and brainstem can be direct and indirect through the BST [Swanson, 2000]. It appears that the central amygdala shares neurochemical features and preferential connections with the lateral BST (BSTL), leading to the concept of central extended amygdala [Alheid and Heimer, 1988; Alheid et al., 1995; McDonald et al., 1999; Bienkowski et al., 2013], which is involved in fear and anxiety responses [Davis et al., 2010]. Regarding the medial amygdala, it shares neurochemical features and preferential connections with the medial BST (BSTM), forming together the medial extended amygdala [Alheid et al., 1995; McDonald et al., 1999; Dong et al., 2001; Bienkowski et al., 2013], which plays a key role in social behavior and cognition [DeVries and Miller, 1998; Newman, 1999; Young and Wang, 2004; Choi et al., 2005]. However, the medial amygdala and the BSTM also project to the central amygdala and the BSTL [Canteras et al., 1995; Dong and Swanson, 2004; Bienkowski et al., 2013], and are able to modulate fear responses by social cues [Ulrich-Lai and Herman, 2009].

In addition, pallial and subpallial parts of the mammalian amygdala contain different subpopulations of neurons. For example, the central amygdala includes distinct subtypes of GABAergic neurons that inhibit each other, and become active (on cells) or inactive (off cells) during fear responses [Cicchi et al., 2010; Hausenback et al., 2010; Tye et al., 2011; Pare and Duvarci, 2012; Ye and Veinante, 2019; Moscarello and Penzo, 2022]. Moreover, while the subpallial extended amygdala is typically considered to be composed of GABAergic neurons [Swanson and Petrovich, 1998], in mammals it also contains subsets of glutamatergic neurons [Csáki et al., 2000; Bian et al., 2008; Hong et al., 2014], raising questions on their origin(s), as well as on their function(s). Thus, we are still far from understanding how these different cell subtypes of the amygdala interact to regulate emotions and social behaviors.

Considering its relevant role for survival and reproduction, one may expect a high degree of conservation in the amygdala. In contrast to this, the amygdala – most particularly its pallidal division – is highly divergent, and its identification in sauropsids is highly controversial [reviewed by Medina et al., 2017; Pessoa et al., 2019]. Even in the subpallium, which is highly conserved between mammals and birds [Reiner et al., 2004; Belgard et al., 2013], researchers have found important difficulties to identify typical amygdala subdivisions such as the central amygdala nucleus [reviewed by Reiner et al., 2004; Kuenzel et al., 2011]. Studying how this structure evolved can help to better understand basic principles on its organization, but also to identify variations in neural mechanisms that are behind different adaptations in the regulation of essential behaviors. However, comparing the adult brain of distant groups of vertebrates is extremely complicated, particularly in brain regions that have undergone great divergence, such as the telencephalon [Reiner et al., 2004]. One way to solve this is by comparison of embryonic brains, since it is at early stages when the neural tube of different vertebrates shows more clearly its morphoplan (or building plan, in German Bauplan), and thus it is at early stages when identification of homologous units becomes easier [Striedter, 1997; Puelles and Medina, 2002; Nieuwenhuys

and Puelles, 2016; Medina et al., 2022]. This approach is also useful to identify the homologous cell subpopulations of the amygdala, derived from homologous embryonic divisions, in the brain of different animals.

Main Text

The evolutionary developmental neurobiology approach and its contribution to understanding the amygdala

Evolutionary developmental biology (evodevo) conceptualizes evolution as heritable changes in development [Moczek et al., 2015]. By analyzing expression and function of genes involved in regionalization and morphogenesis across taxa, the evodevo approach has made it possible to successfully address fundamental, long-standing questions in biology, such as the origins of novelty and the causes of variation (i.e. divergence) [reviewed by Moczek et al., 2015]. It has also helped to identify obscure, hidden cases of homology (particularly helpful in cases of high divergence), and to distinguish between homology (inherited from common ancestor) and analogy (due to phenotypic convergence) [Carroll, 2005; Moczek et al., 2015].

The evodevo approach has proven to be extremely useful when applied to a complex organ such as the vertebrate brain [Puelles and Medina, 2002; Medina, 2007; for discussions on homology in the nervous system including a developmental perspective, see also excellent publications by Striedter and Northcutt, 1991; Nieuwenhuys, 1998; Striedter, 1998, 1999; Nieuwenhuys and Puelles, 2016; García-Moreno and Molnár, 2020]. This approach has been particularly relevant when trying to understand the highly divergent telencephalon [Puelles et al., 2000; reviewed by Medina et al., 2011, 2017, 2022]. Comparative embryonic genoarchitecture studies rely on the combinatorial expression patterns of highly conserved developmental regulatory genes, encoding transcription factors and signaling proteins involved in patterning, regionalization and other early developmental events, which are analyzed within the context of the topological framework of the neural tube for identification of

homologous divisions [Puelles and Medina, 2002; Nieuwenhuys and Puelles, 2016]. These studies have helped to better delineate the two major divisions of the telencephalon, pallium and subpallium, and its subdivisions in different vertebrate groups, including jawless fishes, jawed fishes, amphibians, and different amniotes [Fernández et al., 1998; Puelles et al., 2000; Murakami et al., 2001; Bachy et al., 2002; Brox et al., 2003, 2004; Wullimann and Mueller, 2004; Abellán and Medina, 2009; Abellán et al., 2009; Medina and Abellán, 2009; Moreno et al., 2009, 2012, 2018; González et al., 2014; Sugahara et al., 2017; Desfilis et al., 2018]. In the context of the present review, these studies – in combination with experimental data on fate mapping - have helped to delineate pallial and subpallial divisions of the amygdala in the telencephalon of different taxa [Medina and Abellán, 2009; Moreno et al., 2009; Medina et al., 2011, 2022; Vicario et al., 2014, 2015, 2017; Porter and Mueller, 2020; García-Calero et al., 2020, 2021; Rodríguez-Moldes et al., 2021]. Based on the function of the different regulatory genes expressed in these divisions, these studies provide causal explanations for the production of glutamatergic neurons in the pallium, and GABAergic neurons in the subpallium [Hevner et al., 2001; Stühmer et al., 2002; Osório et al., 2010; Le et al., 2017; Lindtner et al., 2019]. Moreover, in addition to pallium and subpallium, we recently found in mammals and sauropsids a third major radial histogenetic division of the telencephalon located at the frontier with the hypothalamus, called the telencephalon-opto-hypothalamic domain (TOH), which produces a large subpopulation of glutamatergic neurons for the extended amygdala [Morales et al., 2021; Metwalli et al., 2022]. This division was previously included as a dorsal part of the supraopto-paraventricular hypothalamic domain (SPV), characterized by expression of the transcription factor *Otp* [Bardet et al., 2008; García-Moreno et al., 2010; Morales-Delgado et al., 2011; Ferran et al., 2015], but based on its early expression of the telencephalic transcription factor *Foxg1*, we considered it a new division of the telencephalon, different from the pallium and the subpallium [Morales et al., 2021; Metwalli et al., 2022]. Below, we will discuss on the contributions to the amygdala from the

three major embryonic divisions of the telencephalon, mainly focusing on amniotes. For the amygdala of amniotes, the readers are referred to the articles by Rodríguez-Moldes [2021], Jiménez and Moreno [2022], Mueller [2022], Wullimann [2022] and Tosches and col. [Deryckere et al., 2022] in this special issue/article collection, as well as those by Moreno and González [2006] and López et al., [2022].

Pallial amygdala

Discussions on the identification of the pallial amygdala in sauropsids were accompanied by controversy on the dorsal ventricular ridge, a large pallial territory located above the pallio-subpallial boundary claimed by some authors to be comparable to the lateral neocortex (as a field or at the level of specific cell groups, as proposed by Karten [1997]; see also Reiner [1991, 1993]; Butler [1994]; and Butler et al. [2011]), or to the claustrum and/or the pallial amygdala by others [Bruce and Neary, 1995c; Striedter, 1997; Puelles, 2001; Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007]. While homology to the neocortex was mostly based on similarity of sensory thalamic inputs and motor outputs, homology to the claustrum and/or pallial amygdala was based on topological position during development [Striedter, 1997; Puelles, 2001] plus selected patterns of connections, such as projections to the hypothalamus [Bruce and Neary, 1995c; Martínez-García et al., 2002]. The advent of comparative embryonic gene expression data pushed the balance towards the DVR-claustrum-pallial amygdala homology [Puelles et al., 2000; see also discussion by Aboitiz et al., 2003]. This was based on data on combinatorial expression patterns of genes encoding transcription factor (such as *Emx1*, *Emx2*, *Pax6*) known to play key roles in early regionalization and specification of the pallium, which together with topology led to a divisional scheme of four pallial divisions (medial, dorsal, lateral and ventral) comparable across amniotes, and to a new understanding of the areas derived from each division [Puelles et al., 2000]. In addition, all of these pallial divisions

express transcription factors involved in production and differentiation of glutamatergic neurons, such as Tbr1 and Tbr2 [Bulfone et al., 1999; Puelles et al., 2000; Abellán et al., 2009; Medina and Abellán, 2009; Moreno et al., 2010; Desfilis et al., 2018]. According to this scheme, the neocortex was found to derive from the dorsal pallium and as such was compared to the avian Wulst [Puelles et al., 2000]. In contrast, the pallial claustramygdaloid region was proposed to derive from the lateral and ventral pallium [Puelles et al., 2000; Medina et al., 2004], and was compared to the DVR of sauropsids [Puelles et al., 2000; Puelles, 2001; Abellán et al., 2009]. More recently, these proposals have been refined based on new data and updated interpretations of the pallial divisions and their derivatives [Medina et al., 2017, 2022; Puelles et al., 2017, 2019; Desfilis et al., 2018; see also Moreau et al., 2021]. One of the most important aspects to remark is that the lateral pallium does not participate in the formation of the amygdala, implying that the claustrum and the pallial amygdala have origins in different pallial sectors and that it makes no sense to talk about the claustramygdaloid region as done before [Puelles et al., 2017; see more below].

The use of gene expression data applied to understanding pallial evolution did not end with the controversy on the DVR homology and on the identification of the pallial amygdala (and the neocortex) in non-mammalian amniotes. About a decade after the publication of the first comparative embryonic genoarchitecture study by Puelles and col. [2000], other authors started to publish comparative gene expression data that raised questions on the DVR-claustramygdaloid homology. Some of the studies focused on molecular identification of cell types in the adult pallium, and claimed that the sauropsidian pallia, including the DVR, contain neuron types with molecular profiles comparable to those of cells in the deep layers (5, 6), granular layer (layer 4) and upper layers (2, 3) of the neocortex [Dugas-Ford et al., 2012; Briscoe et al. 2018; Briscoe and Ragsdale, 2018]. These studies defended homology at cell type level (resembling Karten's proposal), independent of the topological position and embryonic origin of those cells. However, the latter information is critical for identification of homologies

and for distinction between homologies and analogies [Puelles and Medina, 2002; Nieuwenhuys and Puelles, 2016; García-Moreno and Molnár, 2020]. Another study analyzed transcriptome of different pallial divisions, comparing adult mouse and juvenile chicken, and found that the molecular profile of the chicken DVR (nidopallium, mesopallium, arcopallium) was not similar either to that of the neocortex or to that of the pallial amygdala [Belgard et al., 2013]. The latter authors interpreted that the dissimilar patterns found even in cases of pallial sectors of identical embryonic origin (such as ventrocaudal parts of the avian DVR and the mammalian pallial amygdala) were due to the high divergence of the avian and mammalian pallium during evolution, with which we completely agree [discussed by Medina et al., 2022].

Global transcriptome studies have the handicap that they cannot discriminate between the highly diverse cell types found in any adult brain sector, which includes different types of glial cells and neurons. In the adult pallium, we find not only locally born glutamatergic neurons, but also neuron subsets that migrate from other embryonic domains of the pallium (also glutamatergic), the subpallium (mostly GABAergic interneurons) [Bielle et al., 2005; Medina and Abellán, 2009; Medina et al., 2017; Ruiz-Reig et al., 2017; García-Moreno et al., 2018; García-Moreno and Molnár, 2020] or other divisions [García-Moreno et al., 2010; Morales et al., 2022]. This problem has been recently solved by using single-cell transcriptome of pallial neurons of a turtle species [Tosches et al., 2018] and the zebra finch [Colquitt et al., 2021], and comparing the results to those of mouse. When the analysis is restricted to glutamatergic neurons and focused on expression of genes encoding transcription factors, it appears that neurons of the sauropsid DVR show significant similarity to those of the mammalian pallial amygdala, but not to those of the neocortex [Tosches et al., 2018; Colquitt et al., 2021]. In particular, these results show similarity of the anterior DVR of turtle with the lateral nucleus of the basal amygdala complex (both including thalamorecipient nuclei), while the posterior DVR of turtle appears similar to the rest of the pallial amygdala [Tosches et al., 2018; see also

results on song related cell groups of songbird DVR, by Colquitt et al., 2021]. In contrast, when the analysis is done using activity-related genes, the results show similarity between sauropsidian DVR and neocortex, suggesting convergence at the level of activity-related genes [Colquitt et al., 2021; Colquitt, 2022, this issue]. A pending question is to analyze the transcriptome of progenitor cells from different pallial divisions at early stages of development, a time when variations are more limited [at genetic and morphological levels; Carroll et al., 2001; Carroll, 2008], making comparison across species and identification of homologies easier [Puelles and Medina, 2002; Medina, 2007; Medina et al., 2013, 2022]. To know the origin and subsequent steps of the development of neurons can make the comparisons across species more meaningful because it can help to better understand cases of evolutionary divergence (by answering what changed, when did it and how), and to discriminate between similarity due to inheritance from common ancestry (i.e. homology) versus similarity due to convergence [like the acquisition of similar functions, such as infrared vision; Yokoyama et al., 2011]. In the latter case, the similarity is usually related to convergence in expression of activity-related genes, which are subjected to lower constraints for evolutionary variation [Carroll, 2008; Peter and Davidson, 2011; discussed by Medina et al., 2022]. This might be the case for specific functional systems of the sauropsidian DVR and the mammalian neocortex [Pfenning et al., 2014; Colquitt et al., 2021]. For this reason, expression of activity-related genes alone is not a valid criterion for identification of homologies [discussed by Medina et al., 2013, 2022].

Overall, the available data on embryonic origin and genoarchitecture, together with data on adult single cell transcriptome provide a solid support for the homology of a large part of the DVR and the pallial amygdala. Both derive from ventrointermediate/ventrocaudal pallial sectors, initially included as part of the ventral pallium, and are homologous as fields [reviewed by Medina et al., 2022], although they may also contain subsets of newly evolved, non-homologous cells [Puelles and Medina, 2002; Medina, 2007]. This large pallial territory has been

subdivided [five radial subunits identified in the pallial amygdala by García-Calero et al., 2020; several radial subunits also found in the ventrointermediate and ventrocaudal DVR of sauropsids that are molecularly visible; Redies et al., 2001; Abellán et al., 2009; reviewed by Medina et al., 2022], but the comparison of radial subunits between amniotes is far from being clear. In general, the sectors producing the pallial amygdala are now recognized to locate caudal to those producing the olfactory bulb [see discussion by Desfilis et al., 2018] and piriform/endopiriform region [García-Calero et al., 2020]. The ventrointermediate/ventrocaudal pallial sectors producing the pallial amygdala and homologous sectors in the DVR of sauropsids (including part of the avian nidopallium and the arcopallium, and the corresponding parts in non-avian reptiles) express similar sets of regulatory genes from early embryonic stages, such as those encoding the transcription factors *Lhx9* and *Nr2f2/COUP-TFII* [García-López et al., 2008; Abellán et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2013; Tang et al., 2012; Alzu'bi et al., 2017; Desfilis et al., 2018; García-Calero et al., 2021; Medina et al., 2022], which maintain their expression throughout ontogenesis [Jarvis et al., 2013; Gedman et al., 2021]. *Nr2f2/COUP-TFII* plays a critical role in the development of the pallial amygdala, based on the severe malformation of this structure in knockout mice [Tang et al., 2012]. Regarding *Lhx9*, it has been identified as a key gene in this region not only in amniotes [Abellán et al., 2009; Medina et al., 2011, 2017; Chen et al., 2013; Desfilis et al., 2018; Gedman et al., 2021], but also in amphibians and fishes [Moreno et al., 2004; Rodríguez-Moldes et al., 2021; Jiménez and Moreno, 2022, present issue]. In addition to these genes, the ventrocaudal pallium of mouse (producing the posteromedial cortical amygdalar area and subjacent amygdalohippocampal nucleus), chicken (arcopallium) and a lacertid lizard (posterior DVR) show high expression of other transcription factors, such as *Emx1* [Puelles et al., 2000; Chen et al., 2013; Medina et al., 2017; Desfilis et al., 2018; Medina et al., 2022]. The pallial amygdala and its homologues in non-mammals have also undergone important divergence during evolution, including gene expression, cell dispersion, relative size and

morphogenesis of different radial subunits (likely accompanied by divergence in the production of some subsets of cells). For example, the ventral pallium of mouse includes a subset of progenitor cells with transitory early expression of the transcription factor *Dbx1*, but this is not so in sauropsids [Bielle et al., 2005]. In mouse, *Emx1* cells derived from ventrocaudal pallium appear to spread tangentially to other subunits that produce the pallial amygdala [Medina et al., 2017], but this may not be so in sauropsids, based on the scarcity of pallio-pallial migrations in these animals [García-Moreno et al., 2018]. The *Emx1*-expressing posterior subunit (posterior DVR) is larger in some species than in others, but it has undergone different evolutionary trajectories in different species [discussed by Medina et al., 2017; see also Striedter and Northcutt, 2020]: in snakes and lizards with highly developed vomerolfactory system, this division produces a remarkable structure called nucleus sphericus, not found in avian sauropsids and in mammals [Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007]. In mammals, it appears to correspond to the posteromedial cortical amygdalar area, which locates in the same radial unit and receives vomerolfactory inputs [reviews by Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007; Medina et al., 2017]. In birds, with a greatly diminished or absent vomerolfactory system, the ventrocaudal pallium is relatively large (especially in some groups), but this division produces nuclei organized in a completely different way, and include cell subgroups projecting to premotor/motor centers and, in some species, involved in motor control of song-related muscles [Davies et al., 1997; Dubbeldam et al., 1997; Jarvis et al., 2005]. However, independent of these divergences, the DVR of different sauropsids and the pallial amygdala of mammals share some features likely inherited from the most recent common ancestor, as explained next.

Regarding connections, the DVR shows patterns similar to those of the basal complex of the amygdala [see reviews by Bruce and Neary, 1995c; Puelles, 2001; Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007, 2008; Medina et al., 2017, 2019; Pessoa et al., 2019; for DVR connections of non-avian reptiles, see also articles by Lanuza et al., 1997, 1998; Novejarque et al., 2004; for DVR connections of birds, see Davies et

al., 1997; Dubbeldam et al., 1997; Kröner and Güntürkün, 1999; Atoji et al., 2006; Hanics et al., 2017; Wild, 2017]. In particular, the DVR (nidopallium and arcopallium in birds) has sensory inputs from thalamic nuclei of the intermediate and ventral tiers (in mammals giving rise to the posterior intralaminar/paralaminar and medial geniculate nuclear complexes), extensive pallio-pallial connections (including with dorsal and medial pallia) involved in association [Lanuza et al., 1998; Kröner and Güntürkün, 1999], and projections to the basal ganglia, the subpallial extended amygdala, the hypothalamus and the brainstem [Lanuza et al., 1997; Novejarque et al., 2004; Hanics et al., 2017; Wild, 2017].

As explained in the Introduction, the extensive pallio-pallial associative connections, in which the basal complex of the mammalian amygdala is engaged, are behind its role in emotion-related memories, such as fear conditioning and taste aversion, in social cognition, and in regulation of attention, motivation, and decision making [Phelps and LeDoux, 2005; Todd and Anderson, 2009]. Through its projections to the basal ganglia, subpallial amygdala and hypothalamus, the basal amygdalar complex is also capable of regulating reward and goal-directed behavior, emotion-related responses (fear/avoidance behavior), and different aspects of social behavior, and this appears to be similar for the homologous region of sauropsids [Martínez-García et al., 2008; Hanics et al., 2017; Medina et al., 2017, 2019]. In birds, the intermediate/caudal nidopallium and the arcopallium become active following diverse socio-emotional experiences [Bock et al., 2005; Cross et al., 2013; Mayer et al., 2017], and the arcopallium has been involved in fear/avoidance behavior [Saint-Dizier et al., 2009], in food aversion [Tokarev et al., 2011], regulation of feeding behavior [da Silva et al., 2009] and social facilitation [Xin et al., 2017]. The avian caudolateral nidopallium (NCL) has also been involved in associative learning, working memory and decision making [Güntürkün, 2005], and in value coding relative to reward [Dykes et al., 2018]. The latter evidences have usually been interpreted in context of comparison to the mammalian prefrontal cortex, considered analog of NCL [Güntürkün, 2005],

but it is important to remark that the basal complex of the amygdala, which contains the natural NCL homologue, is also involved in these functions [Martínez-García et al., 2007; Pessoa et al., 2019]. Thus, considering this homology is relevant to further evaluate how the NCL and other parts of the avian nidopallium and arcopallium (and the DVR of non-avian reptiles) compare to the pallial amygdala to understand better conserved versus divergent aspects of its structural and functional organization [see further discussion by Martínez-García et al., 2007, and Medina et al., 2017]. Among the divergent patterns, it is worth to remark that the nidopallium/arcopallium of some avian groups have independently evolved specialized cell groups/nuclei and pathways for motor control of vocalization [Striedter, 1994; Jarvis et al., 2014]. In some of these areas (such as nucleus robustus of the arcopallium), there is functional convergence (including at gene expression level) with the human motor cortex that regulates speech [Pfenning et al., 2014; Colquitt et al., 2021]. Even in these remarkable cases, better discrimination between homologies and analogies can contribute to a deeper understanding of the observed differences in connectivity patterns and areas involved in the brain. Deeper search on similarities and differences of homologous structures may even help to discover previously unnoticed functions, such as the role of the pallial and subpallial amygdala of mammals in emotion- and social-related vocalizations [Choi and Brown, 2003; Gadziola et al., 2012; Ma and Kanwal, 2014]. Most tetrapods (also chicken and other non-vocalizer birds) show such emotion/social-related vocalizations and the amygdala may be part of the brain networks involved in their regulation [Martínez-García et al., 2007; Medina et al., 2017], independent of the specializations found only in some groups. Better discrimination between homologies and analogies can also help to understand better how ecological and social adaptations of different species relate to variations in size and complexity of different pallial divisions and subdivisions that give rise to the different cell groups of the pallial amygdala, and can guide us in the identification of molecular mechanisms that contributed to those changes. For example, this might help to

unravel how differences in ecological niches and social habits might have influenced on the relative size and relevance of different functional systems.

Subpallial/TOH extended amygdala

Identification of the centromedial extended amygdala in sauropsids was initially based on its location in the ventral telencephalon, chemoarchitecture and connections [reviewed by Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007, 2008; Reiner et al., 2004; Yamamoto et al., 2005; Kuenzel et al., 2011]. The use of comparative embryonic genoarchitecture supported their subpallial origin and helped to better define the distinct cellular subgroups that constitute the central and medial extended amygdala in birds [Vicario et al., 2014, 2015, 2017; Medina et al., 2017; Pross et al., 2022] and non-avian reptiles [Moreno et al., 2010, 2012], and to compare them to those of mammals [García-López et al., 2008; Hirata et al., 2009; Carney et al., 2010; Waclaw et al., 2010; Bupesh et al., 2011a,b; Morales et al., 2021]. Like in mammals, these subpallial areas in sauropsids express genes involved in the production and differentiation of GABAergic neurons, such as *Dlx2/5* [Puelles et al., 2000; Bardet et al., 2006; Desfilis et al., 2018], and are rich in GABAergic neurons [Abellán and Medina, 2009]. Combinatorial expression of *Dlx2/5*, *Nkx2.1* and *Shh* also allow the parcellation of the subpallium into striatal, pallidal and preoptic divisions [Puelles et al., 2000; Abellán and Medina, 2009; Bardet et al., 2010; Desfilis et al., 2018]. In addition, recent studies identified the TOH as a new radial telencephalic subdivision that produces subpopulations of glutamatergic cells for the extended amygdala in mammals and sauropsids [Morales et al., 2021; Metwalli et al., 2022]. According to these studies, the TOH is located at the transition between the subpallium and the alar hypothalamus, and expresses the transcription factors *Foxg1* (which defines the telencephalon), *Otp* and *Sim1* (until now, the latter were thought to be distinctive of the paraventricular hypothalamus, but not the telencephalon) [Morales et al., 2021; Metwalli et al., 2022]. Notably, TOH produces a large group of glutamatergic cells coexpressing *Foxg1*, *Otp* and/or *Sim1* that migrate radially to part of the medial

extended amygdala. Smaller subsets of cells also invade tangentially other parts of the extended amygdala. Thus, the extended amygdala includes both GABAergic neurons (with subpallial origin) and glutamatergic neurons (mostly derived from TOH, but with additional contributions, as explained below). Therefore, although this region is usually considered as the subpallial extended amygdala, a part of it develops from the TOH radial histogenetic domain.

Central extended amygdala (EAce). In birds, it includes the BSTL, several nuclei/areas comparable to the central amygdala and the intercalated amygdalar cells, with embryonic origin, gene expression profiles and connections similar to those of mammals [Atoji et al., 2006; Martínez-García et al., 2007, 2008; Kuenzel et al., 2011; Vicario et al., 2014, 2015, 2017; Medina et al., 2017]. In non-avian reptiles, the EAce is usually referred to as the striato-amygdaloid transition area (SAT), although its posteromedial part is distinguished as BSTL by some authors [Bruce and Neary, 1995a,b; Lanuza et al., 1997; Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007, 2008; Novejarque et al., 2004]. There is evidence showing that the SAT and the avian BSTL are involved in fear and stress responses [Davies et al., 2002; Nagarajan et al., 2014]. In birds, the BSTL becomes active in stressful situations [Nagarajan et al., 2014] and is part of a network regulating stress, receiving input from pallial amygdalar areas [Atoji et al., 2006] involved in fear behavior [Saint-Dizier et al., 2009] and projecting to the paraventricular hypothalamic nucleus [Atoji et al., 2006], which is also involved in regulating acute and chronic stress [Nagarajan et al., 2014]. Like in mammals, avian BSTL projections also reach the lateral hypothalamus, the periaqueductal gray, the parabrachial nucleus, the solitary nucleus and the motor nucleus of the vagus [Berk, 1987; Atoji et al., 2006], suggesting that it also plays a role in autonomic and somatomotor responses to stressful stimuli. In chicken, the nuclei of the EAce are better defined at about the level of the anterior commissure, although some subdivisions extend rostral and caudal to the commissural levels [Vicario et al., 2014; Pross et al., 2022]. This appears to be similar in non-avian reptiles, where comparable cell groups are seen well at the levels of the anterior and pallial

commissures [Bruce and Neary, 1995b; also see Figure 3a,b in Moreno et al., 2012]. At commissural levels, the different cell groups that constitute the avian EAcE extend from the ventral horn of the lateral ventricle to the boundary with the arcopallium, just above the lateral branch of the anterior commissure, and are traversed by the dorsal bundles of the amygdalofugal tract [Vicario et al., 2014; Pross et al., 2022].

Classically, the mammalian BSTL was considered a ‘pallidal-like’ nucleus while the central amygdala was ‘striatal-like’ [Swanson and Petrovich, 1998], and the first embryonic genoarchitecture studies appeared to support this idea based on combinatorial expression of the subpallial transcription factors *Dlx5*, *Nkx2.1*, and *Lhx6* [the latter two, typical of the pallidal embryonic domain and its derivatives; Puelles et al., 2000; Medina et al., 2004; García-López et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2008]. However, new studies combining gene expression and migration assays showed a more complex situation (see Table): (1) The BSTL contains not only *Nkx2.1* pallidal cells, but also subpopulations of tangentially migrated ‘striatal’ cells (i.e. *Pax6* and *Islet1* expressing cells derived from the dorsal and ventral striatal embryonic divisions, respectively) [Bupesh et al., 2011b]. (2) The central amygdala contains two types of striatal cells, expressing the transcription factors *Pax6* and *Islet1*, derived from the dorsal and ventral striatal embryonic divisions, respectively [Waclaw et al., 2010; Bupesh et al., 2011b]; most *Pax6* occupy the capsular and lateral subdivisions of the nucleus, while *Islet1* cells are found in lateral and medial subdivisions. In addition, the central amygdala includes a subpopulation of cells derived from the caudoventral pallidal division (also known as diagonal domain), that expresses *Nkx2.1* and *Lhx6* [García-López et al., 2008; Bupesh et al., 2011b; see also Real et al., 2009 and Puelles et al., 2016]. Regarding the intercalated amygdalar cells, they appear to derive from the dorsal striatal embryonic division and express *Dlx5*, *Pax6* and other transcription factors such as *FoxP2* [García-López et al., 2008; Kaoru et al., 2010; Bupesh et al., 2011b].

Like in mammals, the BSTL and the central amygdala of sauropsids have a mixture of neurons derived from the pallidal embryonic division (expressing Nkx2.1 and Lhx6), the ventral striatal embryonic division (expressing Islet1) and the dorsal striatal embryonic division (expressing Pax6) [Abellán and Medina, 2009; Moreno et al., 2010, 2012; Vicario et al., 2014, 2015, 2017] (Table and Figure). At least in chicken and zebra finch it also contains a thin lamina of cells, the intercalated amygdalar cells, located at the boundary between the capsular central amygdala and the arcopallium, that derive from the dorsal striatal embryonic division and express Pax6 and FoxP2 [Vicario et al., 2014, 2017]. These different origins likely explain the high diversity of peptidergic neurons found in the BSTL and central amygdala of mammals and sauropsids, containing enkephalin (ENK), somatostatin (SST), substance P, neurotensin and corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF), among others [reviewed by Medina et al., 2017]. Similar peptidergic cells are also found in the central extended amygdala of chicken [Atoji et al., 1996; Richard et al., 2004; Abellán and Medina, 2009; Vicario et al., 2014, 2015], and most of them are also found in the corresponding areas of turtles [Bear and Ebner, 1983; Reiner, et al., 1984, 1987]. In the mammalian central amygdala, these cell types are mostly segregated and constitute different subpopulations, except for a neuron subset found at posterior levels that coexpresses SST, CRF, substance P and neurotensin [McCullough et al., 2018]. In mammals, SST, CRF, substance P and neurotensin cells of BSTL and central amygdala are projection neurons [Moga and Gray, 1985; Moga et al., 1989; Gray and Magnuson, 1992; Gray, 1993], but ENK cells are primarily engaged in connections within the central extended amygdala [central amygdala to BSTL and viceversa; Rao et al., 1987; Poulin et al., 2006]. It appears that EAce cells with different neuropeptide content play different roles in stress regulation [for example, Ciochi et al. 2010; Hausenback et al., 2010; Penzo et al., 2014; see also Moscarello and Penzo, 2022]. Available data also show that, during development, these cells express different sets of transcription factors and originate in distinct embryonic domains, pointing to a development-based molecular code that

contributes to shape amygdalar functional networks. We provide some examples below.

Based on their overlapping distribution, it was previously suggested that most of the ENK cells of lateral EAce and part of those in medial EAce develop from Pax6 cells derived from the dorsal striatal division [Bupesh et al., 2011b; Vicario et al., 2014, 2015]. This was recently shown for a subset of ENK cells that coexpress Pax6 in the avian intercalated amygdalar cells, and some subdivisions of central amygdala and BSTL [Pross et al., 2022]. Regarding the SST cells, these appear to migrate from the ventrocaudal pallidal embryonic division [Bupesh et al., 2011b] and most of them coexpress Nkx2.1 [Pross et al., 2022]. A few of those in avian BSTL also express Islet1, and possibly derive from the preoptic area [as discussed by Pross et al., 2022]. In mammals, the SST cells and the ENK cells (most of which express protein kinase C-delta) of the central amygdala are involved in mutual inhibition and play opposite roles during the conditioned fear response, becoming active (on) or inactive (off) respectively [Cicchi et al., 2010; Hausenback et al., 2010]. SST on-cells of the central amygdala show direct projections to the periaqueductal gray, mediating fear-related freezing [Penzo et al., 2014], while ENK off-cells are only engaged in local connections inside the central amygdala and to the BSTL [Rao et al., 1987; Hausenback et al., 2010]. The BSTL and central amygdala of birds and the corresponding areas of turtles also contain neurons expressing ENK [Reiner et al., 1987] and SST [Bear and Ebner, 1983], and based on coexpression [chicken: Pross et al., 2022] or correlation [slider turtle: Moreno et al., 2010] with Nkx2.1 and Pax6, they appear to have the same embryonic origin as those of mouse. Based on their similar projections to the hypothalamus and brainstem [Bruce and Neary, 1995b; Lanuza et al., 1997; Atoji et al., 2006], it is likely that they play similar roles in regulating fear responses, and this has been shown at least for avian BSTL [Nagarajan et al., 2014; see above]. In addition, the presence of ENK and SST cells with identical origin in the EAce of mammals and sauropsids could mean that on/off systems for

fear control were already present in the central amygdala of early amniotes, which would require further investigation [Medina et al., 2017; Pross et al., 2022].

With respect to the CRF cells of the central amygdala, it was suggested that they develop from *Islet1* cells derived from the ventral striatal embryonic division, but demonstration is pending [Bupesh et al., 2011b; Vicario et al., 2014; Medina et al., 2017]. In mammals, the CRF cells of the central amygdala and BSTL play a key role in sustained fear responses, akin to anxiety [Davis et al., 2010]. Numerous CRF cells have been described in the BSTL of chicken and quail [Panzica et al., 1986; Richard et al., 2004], which may also play a role in anxiety. In fact, the avian BSTL has connections highly similar to those of the mammalian BSTL [Atoji et al., 2006] and has been involved in fear responses [Nagarajan et al., 2014]. However, it seems that these CRF cells of the BSTL evolved independently in birds and mammals, since studies in different species of non-avian reptiles have failed so far to find CRF cells in the area corresponding to the BSTL [Fernández-Llebrez et al., 1988; Mancera et al., 1991; López-Avalos et al., 1993; Silveira et al., 2001]. Nevertheless, the presence of CRF cells in the central amygdala of non-avian reptiles should be re-evaluated using *in situ* hybridization to detect the mRNA.

In addition to subpallial cells, in birds and mammals, the BSTL contains small subsets of neurons that appear to migrate tangentially from the prethalamic eminence (PThE), and express *Pax6*, *Tbr1* and/or *Lhx5* [Abellán and Medina, 2009; Abellán et al., 2010; Bupesh et al., 2011b; Vicario et al., 2014, 2015, 2017; Medina et al., 2017; Ruiz-Reig et al., 2017; Alonso et al., 2020, 2021]. Extremely few *Pax6* cells appear to be present in the slider turtle BSTL, which may also derive from PThE [Moreno et al., 2010]. In addition, the avian BSTL and the capsular central amygdala also contain subsets of *Otp* and *Sim1* cells that migrate tangentially from TOH and SPV core [Metwalli et al., 2022], but similar cells have not been observed in mouse [Morales et al., 2021] and their presence in non-avian reptiles is unknown. While neurons of EAce with subpallial origin are GABAergic, those from the PThE, TOH and SPV core are likely glutamatergic

[Vicario et al., 2015; Metwalli et al., 2022]. How these glutamatergic cells interact with the GABAergic cells of the extended amygdala and in which functional networks they integrate are pending issues.

Medial extended amygdala (EAmE). This includes nuclei identified as the BSTM and the medial amygdala of sauropsids, with embryonic origin, gene expression profiles and connections similar to those of mammals [Bruce and Neary, 1995a; Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007, 2008, 2012; Medina et al., 2017]. Results on comparative embryonic genoarchitecture are greatly contributing to a better delineation and/or understanding of these nuclei in different amniotes, including mammals, birds and non-avian reptiles [reviewed by Medina et al., 2017, 2019]. Studies on cyto- and chemoarchitecture and connections in mammals showed that both the medial amygdala and BSTM have several subdivisions with partially different features, and that distinct subdivisions are involved in partially different functional pathways and regulate distinct aspects of social behavior [Newman, 1999; Swanson, 2000; Dong and Swanson, 2004, 2006; Martínez-García et al., 2012; Otero-García et al., 2014; Cádiz-Moretti et al., 2016]. For example, the posterodorsal subnucleus of the medial amygdala and the posteromedial (principal) subnucleus of the BSTM, which are interconnected, have similar connections with other brain structures that are particularly involved in sexual behavior [Newman, 1999; Swanson, 2000; Dong and Swanson, 2004]. These particular subdivisions of mammalian EAmE share inputs from similar vomerolfactory-related pallial areas and outputs to similar specific preoptic and hypothalamic subdivisions involved in control of neuroendocrine system and sexual behavior, such as the medial preoptic nucleus, the paraventricular hypothalamic nucleus, the ventrolateral part of the ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus, and the ventral premammillary subnucleus [Newman, 1999; Swanson, 2000; Dong and Swanson, 2004]. Moreover, these subdivisions of EAmE are sexually dimorphic and are rich in gonadal receptors [Newman, 1999; Morris et

al., 2008]. In contrast, the posteroventral subnucleus of the medial amygdala and the posterointermediate-posterolateral (transverse-interfascicular) subnuclei of the BSTM preferentially project to anterior (alar) and posterior (basal) hypothalamic areas involved in control of defensive behaviors (such as the dorsomedial part of the ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus and the dorsal premammillary subnucleus) [Canteras et al., 1995; Dong and Swanson, 2004]. In addition, these parts of EAmE also project to some of the areas involved in reproduction (such as the medial preoptic nucleus, mostly its lateral part) [Canteras et al., 1995; Dong and Swanson, 2004], perhaps providing a gate control system of reproduction [Choi et al., 2005]. Regarding the anterior parts of medial amygdala and BSTM, by way of projections to the hypothalamus, they appear involved in regulation of agonistic behaviors, but also project to areas involved in sexual behavior, such as the medial preoptic nucleus [Canteras et al., 1995; Choi et al., 2005; Dong and Swanson, 2006]. In addition, these anterior parts of EAmE also show moderate projections to parts of the central extended amygdala (contributing to regulation of stress and ingestion) and to the midline thalamus (including the paraventricular thalamic nucleus), thus contributing to modulate pallial and subpallial functions [Canteras et al., 1995; Dong and Swanson, 2006].

Based on the connectivity patterns and location in the subpallium, Swanson and collaborators proposed that the mammalian medial amygdala and BSTM were organized as a striato-pallidal-like system specialized in control of social behaviors, with the medial amygdala being striatal-like and BSTM considered pallidal-like (BSTM) [Swanson, 2000; Dong and Swanson, 2004, 2006]. However, based on its development, neuron composition and connections, the situation is much more complex. Regarding its embryonic origin, no part of the EAmE originates in the striatal embryonic domain, but it derives from the ventrocaudal pallidal (diagonal) and preoptic divisions, which express Nkx2.1, Lhx6 and/or Sonic hedgehog (Shh) and Dbx1 during development [García-López et al., 2008; Hirata et al., 2009; Carney et al., 2010; Bupesh et al., 2011a; Lischinsky et al.,

2017]. These subpallial embryonic domains were thought to be the major contributors to the development of the EAmE [García-López et al., 2008; Hirata et al., 2009; Carney et al., 2010; Bupesh et al., 2011a; Lischinsky et al., 2017], and the neurons with subpallial origin were shown to be GABAergic [Hirata et al., 2009; Carney et al., 2010]. In addition to this, other domains of the pallium (ventral/ventrocaudal pallial divisions), alar hypothalamus and prethalamic eminence were proposed to produce minor or moderate populations of glutamatergic neurons that migrate tangentially to the EAmE [Abellán et al., 2010, 2013; García-Moreno et al., 2010; Ruiz-Reig et al., 2017; Medina et al., 2017]. However, recent results of our laboratory showed the existence of a new radial histogenetic division in the telencephalon called TOH that produces a large population of glutamatergic neurons for the medial amygdala and BSTM [Morales et al., 2021]. Moreover, this study found that the TOH-derived glutamatergic neurons of EAmE are projection neurons [Morales et al., 2021], which agrees with the findings of large subpopulations of glutamatergic projection neurons in the medial amygdala and BSTM [Csáki et al., 2000; Bian et al., 2008; Kiss et al., 2011; Hong et al., 2014]. The TOH includes the dorsal subdivision of the supraopto-paraventricular domain or SPV, characterized by Foxg1/Otp coexpression, and accounts for most of the migration of glutamatergic cells from hypothalamus to EAmE found by García-Moreno et al. [2010]. Based on its expression of the telencephalic transcription factor Foxg1, this subdivision was proposed to be part of the telencephalon, while according to this view only the SPV core (which expresses Otp but not Foxg1) remained as part of the hypothalamus [Morales et al., 2021].

Interestingly, neurons with different origins have different molecular profiles and are engaged in different connections and functions, providing a developmental-based code for the formation of brain functional pathways and for understanding how the brain regulates behavior [García-López et al., 2008; Medina et al., 2011, 2017; Sokolowski and Corbin, 2012; Lischinsky et al., 2017; Morales et al., 2021] (see Table). Neurons of medial amygdala and BSTM derived from the

ventrocaudal pallidal domain express Lhx6, and preferentially occupy the anterior and posteromedial parts of BSTM, and the anterior and posterodorsal subnuclei of the medial amygdala [García-López et al., 2008; Carney et al., 2010]. It appears that these cells continue to express Lhx6 in adult rodents, become active by exposure to sex-related odors and project to preoptic and hypothalamic areas involved in sexual behavior [Choi et al., 2005]. Subsets of pallidal/diagonal-derived neurons of the medial amygdala express somatostatin or nitric oxide synthase [Carney et al., 2010], and both subtypes have been identified as projection neurons to the BSTM, medial preoptic nucleus and/or hypothalamus [McDonald, 1987; Tanaka et al., 1997]. EAmc neurons with preoptic origin express Shh and/or Dbx1 [García-López et al., 2008; Hirata et al., 2009; Carney et al., 2010], but it appears that other preoptic-derived cell subtypes express FoxP2 or other transcription factors [Abellán et al., 2010; Carney et al., 2010; Lischinsky et al., 2017]. In the anterior medial amygdala, preoptic-derived Shh/Dbx1 neurons intermingle with neurons of pallidal/diagonal origin (i.e. those expressing Lhx6), while in the posterior medial amygdala Shh/Dbx1 neurons preferentially occupy the core of the posteroventral subnucleus [García-López et al., 2008; Carney et al., 2010; Lischinsky et al., 2017]. The majority of the Dbx1 neurons of preoptic origin are nitrenergic (almost 80% express nitric oxide synthase) [Hirata et al., 2009], a subtype of hypothalamic-projecting neurons of the medial amygdala [Tanaka et al., 1997]. In contrast to Lhx6 cells of pallidal origin, Dbx1 neurons of preoptic origin of the medial amygdala become active after aggressive encounters, but not during mating [Lischinsky et al., 2017].

Regarding the TOH-derived glutamatergic neurons, these coexpress the transcription factors Foxg1 and Otp, and appear to invade radially the posterior part of BSTM, the anterior (perhaps anteroventral) subnucleus of the medial amygdala, and the medial parts of the posterodorsal and posteroventral subnuclei of the medial amygdala [Morales et al., 2021; note that these Otp glutamatergic cells were previously thought to originate in SPV, Bardet et al., 2008; García-Moreno et al., 2010]. In addition, subsets of TOH-derived Foxg1/Otp

cells invade tangentially other parts of the medial extended amygdala (rich in subpallial cells), in addition to other telencephalic areas [Morales et al., 2021, 2022]. Interestingly, these TOH-derived glutamatergic neurons of the medial amygdala and BSTM are projection neurons. Furthermore, the SPV core (expressing *Otp* but not *Foxg1*) also produces minor subpopulations of glutamatergic cells for the medial extended amygdala [Morales et al., 2021] and may be the source of subsets of sexually dimorphic vasopressinergic and oxytocinergic cells found in the BSTM and/or medial amygdala in different mammals [discussed by Medina et al., 2011, 2017; Abellán et al., 2013; Otero-García et al., 2014, 2016]. The latter cells of BSTM appear to be highly sensitive to sex steroids in rodents [Han and De Vries, 2003; De Vries and Panzica, 2006; Rasri et al., 2008].

It appears that *Otp* cells with TOH and SPV origins coexpress *Lhx5* in mouse [García-Moreno et al., 2010; discussed in Metwalli et al., 2022]. In fact, in the anterior medial amygdala, most *Foxg1/Otp* cells are densely grouped in the anteroventral subdivision overlapping cells expressing the transcription factor *Lhx5* [Choi et al., 2005; Abellán et al., 2010]. These specific *Lhx5* cells (presumably glutamatergic) from the anterior medial amygdala have projections to hypothalamic areas involved in defensive behavior, like the anterior (alar) hypothalamus and the dorsomedial part of the ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus [Choi et al., 2005]. In the posterodorsal subnucleus of the medial amygdala, the *Foxg1/Otp* glutamatergic neurons are densely packed in the medial subdivision resemble a population of glutamatergic cells located in the same position, whose activation was shown to inhibit social interaction and promote asocial behavior [Hong et al., 2014; Johnson et al., 2021].

All of these data together show that different neuron populations of EAmE, including several subtypes of GABAergic and glutamatergic neurons with different embryonic origin and molecular profile, regulate different aspects of social behavior. Deciphering the interactions between different subsystems will

surely help to understand how activation of agonistic behaviors also involves inhibition of mating [Choi et al., 2005], and how the balance between social versus asocial behaviors is produced [Hong et al., 2014; Johnson et al., 2021]. This may contribute to understand imbalances between excitation and inhibition found in many mental conditions with social behavior deficits, which involve the amygdala, such as autism spectrum disorder [Gao and Penzes, 2015; Sohal and Rubenstein, 2019].

The medial extended amygdala has been described in different sauropsids (birds and non-avian reptiles) based on position in the posteroventral telencephalon, chemoarchitecture (including the presence of gonadal receptors), inputs from the olfactory/vomerolfactory bulbs and projections to the hypothalamus [Bruce and Neary, 1995a; Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007, 2008; Reiner et al., 2004; Kuenzel et al., 2011; Medina et al., 2017, 2019]. Comparative developmental genoarchitecture studies have greatly helped to better define the extension and various cell subpopulations that constitute the medial amygdala and BSTM of sauropsids, in comparison to those of mammals [Moreno et al., 2010, 2012; Abellán et al., 2013; Medina et al., 2017, 2019].

Regarding the medial amygdala, it is rather small in birds and includes the anteromedial, subpallial part of the so-called nucleus taeniae [Reiner et al., 2004; Kuenzel et al., 2011]. Like the medial amygdala of mammals [García-López et al., 2008; Carney et al., 2010; Bupesh et al., 2011a], this avian nucleus contains neurons derived from the ventrocaudal pallidal (diagonal) embryonic division and from the preoptic division, which respectively express the transcription factors Nkx2.1, Lhx6 (pallidal cells) and/or the signaling protein Shh (preoptic cells) [Abellán and Medina, 2009; Vicario et al., 2017] (Table). In addition, it also contains Otp and Sim1 cells coexpressing Foxg1 derived from TOH [Metwalli et al., 2022]. While pallidal and preoptic cells are likely GABAergic [Abellán and Medina, 2009], those derived from TOH appear to be glutamatergic [Metwalli et al., 2022]. Moreover, the avian medial amygdala contains subsets of Lhx5 and

FoxP2 cells, but it is unclear if these originate in TOH/SPV and/or in other embryonic domains such as the preoptic area (Lhx5 and FoxP2 cells) and the prethalamic eminence (Lhx5 cells) [Abellán et al., 2010; Vicario et al., 2017]. In addition, the avian medial amygdala contains a minor subset of Lhx9 cells that appear to migrate tangentially from the ventral/ventrocaudal pallium, and these are likely glutamatergic [Abellán et al., 2009, 2013; Vicario et al., 2017].

At postcommissural levels, the avian medial amygdala forms with the BSTM a cell continuum parallel to the ventral amygdalofugal tract (the latter runs from the pallial amygdala to the hypothalamus describing an arc). In particular, the BSTM consists of several subcorridors with cells of different origins and molecular profiles, which show a trend to organize in parallel, non-overlapping bands [Medina et al., 2017; Vicario et al., 2017] (Figure). The most medial band is mainly composed of Shh/Islet1 preoptic-derived cells; the intermediate band mostly contains Lhx6 cells derived from the ventrocaudal pallidal embryonic domain [Abellán and Medina, 2009; Medina et al., 2017; Vicario et al., 2017]; and the lateralmost one mainly includes Otp and Sim1 cells coexpressing Foxg1 mostly derived from TOH [Metwalli et al., 2022]. Like in mammals, neurons of the avian BSTM with preoptic and pallidal origins are likely GABAergic [Abellán and Medina, 2009; Abellán et al., 2013; Medina et al., 2017] and appear to include the BSTM1/BSTM2 (or dorsal and ventral) subdivisions previously described [Aste et al., 1998; Jurkevich et al., 1999]. In contrast, Otp and Sim1 cells of the lateral band of BSTM with TOH origin are likely glutamatergic based on expression of VGLUT2 [Metwalli et al., 2022] and appear to correspond to the BSTM3, a subdivision poor in markers of subpallial cells, including Lhx6 and GAD67 [Abellán and Medina, 2008, 2009]. The latter subdivision has also been referred as hypothalamic BSTM based on putative origin of its cells in SPV [Vicario et al., 2017], but according to new data most of these cells really derive from TOH, and only minor cell subsets not coexpressing Foxg1 may originate in SPV core [Metwalli et al., 2022]. Like in mammals, the latter may include subpopulations of vasotocin and mesotocin-containing cells that appear to partially overlap with the preoptic and TOH bands

of BSTM [Vicario et al., 2017; discussed by Medina et al., 2011, 2017; Metwalli et al., 2022].

The medial amygdala of non-avian reptiles contains subpopulations of cells expressing Nkx2.1 and Otp, suggesting the presence of cells of at least pallido-preoptic and TOH/SPV origins [Moreno et al., 2010; Abellán et al., 2013]. Like in birds and mammals, it also appears to include minor subsets of Tbr1 cells and Pax6 cells that may originate in the pallium and/or the prethalamic eminence [Moreno et al., 2010, 2012]. Regarding the BSTM, in lizards it was identified as the interstitial amygdala, which is laterally continuous with the medial amygdala at postcommissural levels [Bruce and Neary, 1995a], and occupies a position very similar to the BSTM of birds [Abellán et al., 2013]. Like in birds, the BSTM of lizards includes a lateral band rich in Foxg/Otp cells derived from TOH, and a medial band with Foxg1 without Otp which likely derives from the subpallium [Metwalli et al., 2022]. The BSTM also appears to be present in turtles, included as part of the preoptic area, and contains Islet1 cells (likely preoptic origin) and Otp cells (likely TOH/SPV origins) [see Figure 6a in Moreno et al., 2012]. Overall, it appears that similar cell populations are found in the EAmE of all sauropsids and mammals, although it is likely that there are differences in their relative abundance in different species, which would require further investigation.

The medial amygdala and BSTM of sauropsids show patterns of connections similar to those of mammalian EAmE, such as inputs from the olfactory/vomerofactory bulbs [Reiner and Karten, 1985; Martínez-García et al., 1991; Halpern and Martínez-Marcos, 2003] and from olfactory and associative parts of the pallial amygdala [Lanuza et al., 1997, 1998; Novejarque et al., 2004; in birds, this includes at least the arcopallium and the pallial part of nucleus taeniae: Cheng et al., 1999; Kröner and Güntürkün, 1999]; in addition, they project to the sexually dimorphic medial preoptic nucleus [Absil et al., 2002], the paraventricular hypothalamic nucleus, and the ventromedial hypothalamus [Bruce and Neary, 1995a; reviewed by Martínez-García et al., 2002, 2007, 2008;

Medina et al., 2017, 2019]. Like in mammals, these avian preoptic/hypothalamic nuclei targeted by EAme have similar functions to those of mammals: the medial preoptic nucleus is involved in male sexual behavior [Panzica et al., 1996, 2001a,b; Balthazart et al., 2001; Balthazart and Ball, 2007]; the paraventricular hypothalamic nucleus is an integral part of the hypothalamo-pituitary-glandular axes for control of stress, reproduction, metabolism and homeostasis, and also regulates the autonomic nervous system by descending projections to the brainstem [De Vries and Panzica, 2006; Kuenzel and Jurkevich, 2010; Smulders, 2021; Grassi et al., 2022]; and the ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus is involved in aspects of sexual behavior and food intake [Kuenzel et al., 1999; Cline et al., 2007; Ritters and Pawlisch, 2007]. The EAme of non-avian reptiles also projects to similar preoptic and hypothalamic nuclei involved in neuroendocrine control and social behavior [Martínez-García et al., 2008; O'Connell and Hofmann, 2011; Kabelik et al., 2021, 2022].

Moreover, similarly to mammalian EAme, the medial amygdala and BSTM of sauropsids contains nitrenergic projection neurons [Brüning, 1993; Brüning et al., 1994; identified as part of the central amygdala by Smeets et al., 1997], somatostatinergic neurons [Pross et al., 2022], gonadal receptors [Foidart et al., 1999], and aromatase-expressing cells (estrogen synthase, transforming testosterone to estradiol; Aste et al., 1998; Balthazart et al., 1998), and are involved in different aspects of sexually dimorphic social behaviors [Ball and Balthazart, 2004; Goodson, 2005; Xie et al., 2010; 2011; reviewed by Kuenzel et al., 2011; Medina et al., 2017, 2019]. Moreover, the pallial amygdala-like areas of the DVR (including the arcopallium and the pallial part of nucleus taeniae) projecting to the EAme of sauropsids have been involved in sociality [Cheng et al., 1999; Mayer et al., 2017; Xin et al., 2017], and all together appear to be part of a social behavior network [reviewed by Medina et al., 2019]. Like in mammals, the BSTM of sauropsids also contains subsets of vasotocin/mesotocin neurons [Aste et al., 1998; Jurkevich et al., 1999] that have also been involved in sexually dimorphic social behaviors [De Vries and Miller, 1998; De Vries and Panzica,

2006; Kelly and Goodson, 2014]. From puberty, the vasotocin-containing cells of avian BSTM are sexually dimorphic [Aste et al., 1998; Jurkevich et al., 1999; Grossmann et al., 2002] and many of them coexpress the neuropeptide galanin [Klein et al., 2006]. In avian BSTM, cells coexpressing vasotocin and galanin are only seen in males but not females, are regulated by sex steroids and appear to play a role in male-specific sociosexual behavior [discussed by Klein et al., 2006]. In females, the avian BSTM does not contain galanin cells. In contrast, in the rat BSTM galanin cells are found in both sexes [Planas et al., 1994], but in males a higher number of them coexpress vasopressin in comparison to females [Planas et al., 1995].

Considering the high diversity of neurons found in the EAmE of sauropsids, more studies are needed to evaluate the specific connections and role of each cell type in the control of different aspects of social behavior. Like in mammals, the EAmE of sauropsids also contains GABAergic and glutamatergic neurons and this seems to be the ancestral condition in amniotes. From now on, it is necessary to evaluate how they interact with each other to promote or inhibit social behaviors, and to study basic principles on a gate control system of reproduction and other behaviors in amniotes.

Conclusion

So far, the evolutionary developmental neurobiology approach has been crucial for identifying homologous cell populations with identical embryonic origins and molecular profiles in the amygdala of different amniotes. In the future, this approach can also contribute to fill the gap between embryonic origin and the functional networks in which cells are engaged, and to a better understanding of the neural control of behavior, emotions and cognition, in which the amygdala plays crucial roles.

Statements

Acknowledgement (optional)

We deeply thank all Agencies that funded our research.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Funding Sources

Funded by grants from the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Agencia Estatal de Investigación, Grant No. PID2019-108725RB-100) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 812777 (H2020-MSCA-ITN-2018-812777). LMo had a predoctoral fellowship from Universitat de Lleida i Ajuts Jade Plus, and a predoctoral contract from IRBLleida/Diputació de Lleida. AG-A had a predoctoral fellowship from Universitat de Lleida i Ajuts Jade Plus, and currently holds a predoctoral contract from AGAUR (Generalitat de Catalunya 2021 FI_B00353). JF also holds a predoctoral contract from AGAUR (Generalitat de Catalunya 2022 FI_B 00848). AHM and AP have contracts as Early-Stage Researchers paid by the H2020-MSCA-ITN-2018-812777 project. The funding agencies did not participate in the research and preparation of the manuscript.

Author Contributions

Loreta Medina and Ester Desfilis designed the manuscript based on the talk they provided at the Karger Workshop in 2021 and on published results of all authors. Loreta Medina wrote the first draft of the manuscript and Ester Desfilis revised it. Antonio Abellán, Lorena Morales, Alessandra Pross, Alek H. Metwalli, Alba González-Alonso, and Júlia Freixes contributed to further revise the manuscript until its final form.

References

1. Abellán A, Medina L. Expression of cLhx6 and cLhx7/8 suggests a pallido-pedunculo-preoptic origin for the lateral and medial parts of the avian bed nucleus of the stria terminalis. *Brain Res Bull.* 2008;75(2-4):299-304. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainresbull.2007.10.034
2. Abellán A, Medina L. Subdivisions and derivatives of the chicken subpallium based on expression of LIM and other regulatory genes and markers of neuron subpopulations during development. *J Comp Neurol.* 2009;515(4):465-501. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22083
3. Abellán A, Legaz I, Vernier B, Rétaux S, Medina L. Olfactory and amygdalar structures of the chicken ventral pallium based on the combinatorial expression patterns of LIM and other developmental regulatory genes. *J Comp Neurol.* 2009;516(3):166-186. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22102
4. Abellán A, Vernier B, Rétaux S, Medina L. Similarities and differences in the forebrain expression of Lhx1 and Lhx5 between chicken and mouse: Insights for understanding telencephalic development and evolution. *J Comp Neurol.* 2010;518(17):3512-3528. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22410
5. Abellán A, Desfilis E, Medina L. The olfactory amygdala in amniotes: an evo-devo approach. *Anat Rec (Hoboken).* 2013;296(9):1317-1332. DOI: 10.1002/ar.22744
6. Aboitiz F, Morales D, Montiel J. The evolutionary origin of the mammalian isocortex: towards an integrated developmental and functional approach. *Behav Brain Sci.* 2003;26(5):535-585. DOI: 10.1017/s0140525x03000128
7. Absil P, Papello M, Viglietti-Panzica C, Balthazart J, Panzica G. The medial preoptic nucleus receives vasotocinergic inputs in male quail: a tract-tracing and immunocytochemical study. *J Chem Neuroanat.* 2002;24(1):27-39. DOI: 10.1016/s0891-0618(02)00017-0
8. Alheid GF, Heimer L. New perspectives in basal forebrain organization of special relevance for neuropsychiatric disorders: the striatopallidal, amygdaloid, and corticopetal components of substantia innominata. *Neuroscience.* 1988;27(1):1-39. DOI: 10.1016/0306-4522(88)90217-5
9. Alheid GF, de Olmos J, Beltramino CA. Amygdala and extended amygdala. In: Paxinos G, editor. *The Rat Nervous System.* San Diego: Academic Press. 1995, p. 495-578.
10. Alonso A, Trujillo CM, Puelles L. Longitudinal developmental analysis of prethalamic eminence derivatives in the chick by mapping of Tbr1 in situ expression. *Brain Struct Funct.* 2020;225(2):481-510. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-019-02015-3

11. Alonso A, Trujillo CM, Puelles L. Quail-chick grafting experiments corroborate that Tbr1-positive eminential prethalamic neurons migrate along three streams into hypothalamus, subpallium and septocommissural areas. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2021;226(3):759-785. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-020-02206-3
12. Alzu'bi A, Lindsay SJ, Harkin LF, McIntyre J, Lisgo SN, Clowry GJ. The Transcription Factors COUP-TFI and COUP-TFII have Distinct Roles in Arealisation and GABAergic Interneuron Specification in the Early Human Fetal Telencephalon. *Cereb Cortex*. 2017;27(10):4971-4987. DOI: 10.1093/cercor/bhx185
13. Aste N, Balthazart J, Absil P, et al. Anatomical and neurochemical definition of the nucleus of the stria terminalis in Japanese quail (*Coturnix japonica*). *J Comp Neurol*. 1998;396(2):141-157.
14. Atoji Y, Shibata N, Yamamoto Y, Suzuki Y. Distribution of neurotensin-containing neurons in the central nervous system of the pigeon and the chicken. *J Comp Neurol*. 1996;375(2):187-211. DOI: 10.1002/(SICI)1096-9861(19961111)375:2<187::AID-CNE2>3.0.CO;2-Z
15. Atoji Y, Saito S, Wild JM. Fiber connections of the compact division of the posterior pallial amygdala and lateral part of the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis in the pigeon (*Columba livia*). *J Comp Neurol*. 2006;499(2):161-182. DOI: 10.1002/cne.21042
16. Bachy I, Berthon J, Rétaux S. Defining pallial and subpallial divisions in the developing *Xenopus* forebrain. *Mech Dev*. 2002;117(1-2):163-172. DOI: 10.1016/s0925-4773(02)00199-5
17. Ball GF, Balthazart J. Hormonal regulation of brain circuits mediating male sexual behavior in birds. *Physiol Behav*. 2004;83(2):329-346. doi:10.1016/j.physbeh.2004.08.020
18. Balthazart J, Ball GF. Topography in the preoptic region: differential regulation of appetitive and consummatory male sexual behaviors. *Front Neuroendocrinol*. 2007;28(4):161-178. DOI: 10.1016/j.yfrne.2007.05.003
19. Balthazart J, Foidart A, Baillien M, Harada N, Ball GF. Anatomical relationships between aromatase and tyrosine hydroxylase in the quail brain: double-label immunocytochemical studies. *J Comp Neurol*. 1998;391(2):214-226.
20. Balthazart J, Stamatakis A, Bacola S, Absil P, Dermon CR. Effects of lesions of the medial preoptic nucleus on the testosterone-induced metabolic changes in specific brain areas in male quail. *Neuroscience*. 2001;108(3):447-466. DOI: 10.1016/s0306-4522(01)00422-5
21. Bardet SM, Cobos I, Puelles E, Martínez-De-La-Torre M, Puelles L. Chicken lateral septal organ and other circumventricular organs form in a striatal subdomain abutting the molecular striatopallidal border. *J Comp Neurol*. 2006;499(5):745-767. DOI: 10.1002/cne.21121

22. Bardet SM, Martinez-de-la-Torre M, Northcutt RG, Rubenstein JL, Puelles L. Conserved pattern of OTP-positive cells in the paraventricular nucleus and other hypothalamic sites of tetrapods. *Brain Res Bull.* 2008;75(2-4):231-235. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainresbull.2007.10.037
23. Bardet SM, Ferran JL, Sanchez-Arrones L, Puelles L. Ontogenetic expression of sonic hedgehog in the chicken subpallium. *Front Neuroanat.* 2010 Jul;4:28. DOI: 10.3389/fnana.2010.00028
24. Bear MF, Ebner FF. Somatostatin-like immunoreactivity in the forebrain of *Pseudemys* turtles. *Neuroscience.* 1983;9(2):297-307. DOI: 10.1016/0306-4522(83)90295-6
25. Belgard TG, Montiel JF, Wang WZ, García-Moreno F, Margulies EH, Ponting PH et al. Adult pallium transcriptomes surprise in not reflecting predicted homologies across diverse chicken and mouse pallial sectors. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2013;110(32):13150-13155. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1307444110
26. Berk ML. Projections of the lateral hypothalamus and bed nucleus of the stria terminalis to the dorsal vagal complex in the pigeon. *J Comp Neurol.* 1987;260(1):140-156. DOI: 10.1002/cne.902600111
27. Bian X, Yanagawa Y, Chen WR, Luo M. Cortical-like functional organization of the pheromone-processing circuits in the medial amygdala. *J Neurophysiol.* 2008;99(1):77-86. DOI: 10.1152/jn.00902.2007
28. Bielle F, Griveau A, Narboux-Nême N, Vigneau S, Sigrist M, Arber S, et al. Multiple origins of Cajal-Retzius cells at the borders of the developing pallium. *Nat Neurosci.* 2005;8(8):1002-1012. DOI: 10.1038/nn1511
29. Bienkowski MS, Wendel ES, Rinaman L. Organization of multisynaptic circuits within and between the medial and the central extended amygdala. *J Comp Neurol.* 2013;521(15):3406-3431. DOI: 10.1002/cne.23356
30. Bock J, Thode C, Hannemann O, Braun K, Darlison MG. Early socio-emotional experience induces expression of the immediate-early gene *Arc/arg3.1* (activity-regulated cytoskeleton-associated protein/activity-regulated gene) in learning-relevant brain regions of the newborn chick. *Neuroscience.* 2005;133(3):625-633. DOI: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2005.02.048
31. Briscoe SD, Ragsdale CW. Molecular anatomy of the alligator dorsal telencephalon. *J Comp Neurol.* 2018;526(10):1613-1646. DOI: 10.1002/cne.24427
32. Briscoe SD, Albertin CB, Rowell JJ, Ragsdale CW. Neocortical Association Cell Types in the Forebrain of Birds and Alligators. *Curr Biol.* 2018;28(5):686-696.e6. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2018.01.036

33. Brox A, Puelles L, Ferreiro B, Medina L. Expression of the genes GAD67 and Distal-less-4 in the forebrain of *Xenopus laevis* confirms a common pattern in tetrapods. *J Comp Neurol*. 2003;461(3):370-393. DOI: 10.1002/cne.10688
34. Brox A, Puelles L, Ferreiro B, Medina L. Expression of the genes *Emx1*, *Tbr1*, and *Eomes (Tbr2)* in the telencephalon of *Xenopus laevis* confirms the existence of a ventral pallial division in all tetrapods. *J Comp Neurol*. 2004;474(4):562-577. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20152
35. Bruce LL, Neary TJ. The limbic system of tetrapods: a comparative analysis of cortical and amygdalar populations. *Brain Behav Evol*. 1995c;46(4-5):224-234. DOI: 10.1159/000113276
36. Bruce LL, Neary TJ. Afferent projections to the ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus in a lizard, *Gekko gecko*. *Brain Behav Evol*. 1995a;46(1):14-29. DOI: 10.1159/000113255
37. Bruce LL, Neary TJ. Afferent projections to the lateral and dorsomedial hypothalamus in a lizard, *Gekko gecko*. *Brain Behav Evol*. 1995b;46(1):30-42. DOI: 10.1159/000113256
38. Brüning G. Localization of NADPH-diaphorase in the brain of the chicken. *J Comp Neurol*. 1993;334(2):192-208. DOI: 10.1002/cne.903340204
39. Brüning G, Wiese S, Mayer B. Nitric oxide synthase in the brain of the turtle *Pseudemys scripta elegans*. *J Comp Neurol*. 1994;348(2):183-206. DOI: 10.1002/cne.903480203
40. Bulfone A, Martinez S, Marigo V, Campanella M, Basile A, Quaderi N, et al. Expression pattern of the *Tbr2 (Eomesodermin)* gene during mouse and chick brain development. *Mech Dev*. 1999;84(1-2):133-138. DOI: 10.1016/s0925-4773(99)00053-2
41. Bupesh M, Legaz I, Abellán A, Medina L. Multiple telencephalic and extratelencephalic embryonic domains contribute neurons to the medial extended amygdala. *J Comp Neurol*. 2011a;519(8):1505-1525. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22581
42. Bupesh M, Abellán A, Medina L. Genetic and experimental evidence supports the continuum of the central extended amygdala and a multiple embryonic origin of its principal neurons. *J Comp Neurol*. 2011b;519(17):3507-3531. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22719
43. Butler AB. The evolution of the dorsal pallium in the telencephalon of amniotes: cladistic analysis and a new hypothesis. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev*. 1994;19(1):66-101. DOI: 10.1016/0165-0173(94)90004-3
44. Butler AB, Reiner A, Karten HJ. Evolution of the amniote pallium and the origins of mammalian neocortex. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 2011;1225:14-27. DOI: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.2011.06006.x

45. Cádiz-Moretti B, Otero-García M, Martínez-García F, Lanuza E. Afferent projections to the different medial amygdala subdivisions: a retrograde tracing study in the mouse. *Brain Struct Funct.* 2016;221(2):1033-1065. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-014-0954-y
46. Canteras NS, Simerly RB, Swanson LW. Organization of projections from the medial nucleus of the amygdala: a PHAL study in the rat [published correction appears in *J Comp Neurol* 1996 May 27;369(2):328-30]. *J Comp Neurol.* 1995;360(2):213-245. DOI: 10.1002/cne.903600203
47. Carney RS, Mangin JM, Hayes L, Mansfield K, Sousa VH, Fishell G, et al. Sonic hedgehog expressing and responding cells generate neuronal diversity in the medial amygdala. *Neural Dev.* 2010 May;5:14. DOI: 10.1186/1749-8104-5-14
48. Carroll SB. Evolution at two levels: on genes and form. *PLoS Biol.* 2005 Jul;3(7):e245.
49. Carroll SB. Evo-devo and an expanding evolutionary synthesis: a genetic theory of morphological evolution. *Cell.* 2008;134(1):25-36. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2008.06.030
50. Carroll SB, Grenier JK, Weatherbee SD. *From DNA to Diversity. Molecular Genetics and the Evolution of Animal Design.* London (UK): Blackwell Science; 2001.
51. Chen CC, Winkler CM, Pfenning AR, Jarvis ED. Molecular profiling of the developing avian telencephalon: regional timing and brain subdivision continuities. *J Comp Neurol.* 2013;521(16):3666-3701. DOI: 10.1002/cne.23406
52. Cheng M, Chaiken M, Zuo M, Miller H. Nucleus taenia of the amygdala of birds: anatomical and functional studies in ring doves (*Streptopelia risoria*) and European starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris*). *Brain Behav Evol.* 1999;53(5-6):243-270. DOI: 10.1159/000006597
53. Choi JS, Brown TH. Central amygdala lesions block ultrasonic vocalization and freezing as conditional but not unconditional responses. *J Neurosci.* 2003;23(25):8713-8721. DOI: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.23-25-08713.2003
54. Choi GB, Dong HW, Murphy AJ, Valenzuela DM, Yancopoulos GD, Swanson LW, et al. *Lhx6* delineates a pathway mediating innate reproductive behaviors from the amygdala to the hypothalamus. *Neuron.* 2005;46(4):647-660. DOI: 10.1016/j.neuron.2005.04.011
55. Cioocchi S, Herry C, Grenier F, Wolff SBE, Letzkus JJ, Vlachos I, et al. Encoding of conditioned fear in central amygdala inhibitory circuits. *Nature.* 2010;468(7321):277-282. DOI: 10.1038/nature09559
56. Cline MA, Nandar W, Rogers JO. Xenin reduces feed intake by activating the ventromedial hypothalamus and influences gastrointestinal transit rate in chicks. *Behav Brain Res.* 2007;179(1):28-32. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbr.2007.01.008

57. Colquitt BM, Merullo DP, Konopka G, Roberts TF, Brainard MS. Cellular transcriptomics reveals evolutionary identities of songbird vocal circuits. *Science*. 2021;371(6530):eabd9704. DOI: 10.1126/science.abd9704
58. Colquitt BM. Organizational conservation and flexibility in the evolution of birdsong and avian motor control. *Brain Behav Evol* 2022;97:255-264. DOI: 10.1159/000525019.
59. Cross DJ, Marzluff JM, Palmquist I, Minoshima S, Shimizu T, Miyaoka R. Distinct neural circuits underlie assessment of a diversity of natural dangers by American crows. *Proc Biol Sci*. 2013 Jul;280(1765):20131046. DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2013.1046
60. Csáki A, Kocsis K, Halász B, Kiss J. Localization of glutamatergic/aspartatergic neurons projecting to the hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus studied by retrograde transport of [³H]D-aspartate autoradiography. *Neuroscience*. 2000;101(3):637-655. DOI: 10.1016/s0306-4522(00)00411-5
61. Davies DC, Csillag A, Székely AD, Kabai P. Efferent connections of the domestic chick archistriatum: a phaseolus lectin anterograde tracing study. *J Comp Neurol*. 1997;389(4):679-693. DOI: 10.1002/(sici)1096-9861(19971229)389:4<679::aid-cne10>3.0.co;2-7
62. Davies DC, Martínez-García F, Lanuza E, Novejarque A. Striato-amygdaloid transition area lesions reduce the duration of tonic immobility in the lizard *Podarcis hispanica*. *Brain Res Bull*. 2002;57(3-4):537-541. DOI: 10.1016/s0361-9230(01)00687-6
63. Davis M, Walker DL, Miles L, Grillon C. Phasic vs sustained fear in rats and humans: role of the extended amygdala in fear vs anxiety. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2010;35(1):105-135. DOI: 10.1038/npp.2009.109
64. da Silva AA, Campanella LC, Ramos MC, Parreira C, Faria MS, Marino-Neto J, et al. Arcopallium, NMDA antagonists and ingestive behaviors in pigeons. *Physiol Behav*. 2009;98(5):594-601. DOI: 10.1016/j.physbeh.2009.09.009
65. Deryckere A, Woych J, Jaeger LCB, Tosches MA. Glutamatergic neuron types in the amygdala of the urodele amphibian *Pleurodeles waltl*. *Brain Behav Evol*. – in press
66. Desfilis E, Abellán A, Sentandreu V, Medina L. Expression of regulatory genes in the embryonic brain of a lizard and implications for understanding pallial organization and evolution. *J Comp Neurol*. 2018;526(1):166-202. DOI: 10.1002/cne.24329
67. de Olmos JS, Heimer L. The concepts of the ventral striatopallidal system and extended amygdala. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 1999;877:1-32. DOI: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.1999.tb09258.x

68. De Vries GJ, Miller MA. Anatomy and function of extrahypothalamic vasopressin systems in the brain. *Prog Brain Res.* 1998;119:3-20. DOI: 10.1016/s0079-6123(08)61558-7
69. De Vries GJ, Panzica GC. Sexual differentiation of central vasopressin and vasotocin systems in vertebrates: different mechanisms, similar endpoints. *Neuroscience.* 2006;138(3):947-955. DOI: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2005.07.050
70. Donaldson ZR, Young LJ. Oxytocin, vasopressin, and the neurogenetics of sociality. *Science.* 2008;322(5903):900-904. DOI: 10.1126/science.1158668
71. Dong HW, Petrovich GD, Swanson LW. Topography of projections from amygdala to bed nuclei of the stria terminalis. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev.* 2001;38(1-2):192-246. DOI: 10.1016/s0165-0173(01)00079-0
72. Dong HW, Swanson LW. Projections from bed nuclei of the stria terminalis, posterior division: implications for cerebral hemisphere regulation of defensive and reproductive behaviors [published correction appears in *J Comp Neurol.* 2004 Jul 5;474(4):603-4]. *J Comp Neurol.* 2004;471(4):396-433. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20002
73. Dong HW, Swanson LW. Projections from bed nuclei of the stria terminalis, anteromedial area: cerebral hemisphere integration of neuroendocrine, autonomic, and behavioral aspects of energy balance. *J Comp Neurol.* 2006;494(1):142-178. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20788
74. Dubbeldam JL, den Boer-Visser AM, Bout RG. Organization and efferent connections of the archistriatum of the mallard, *Anas platyrhynchos* L.: an anterograde and retrograde tracing study. *J Comp Neurol.* 1997;388(4):632-657. DOI: 10.1002/(sici)1096-9861(19971201)388:4<632::aid-cne10>3.0.co;2-n
75. Dugas-Ford J, Rowell JJ, Ragsdale CW. Cell-type homologies and the origins of the neocortex. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2012;109(42):16974-16979. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1204773109
76. Dykes M, Klarer A, Porter B, Rose J, Colombo M. Neurons in the Pigeon Nidopallium Caudolaterale Display Value-Related Activity. *Sci Rep.* 2018 Mar;8(1):5377. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-018-23694-8
77. Fernandez AS, Pieau C, Repérant J, Boncinelli E, Wassef M. Expression of the Emx-1 and Dlx-1 homeobox genes define three molecularly distinct domains in the telencephalon of mouse, chick, turtle and frog embryos: implications for the evolution of telencephalic subdivisions in amniotes. *Development.* 1998;125(11):2099-2111. DOI: 10.1242/dev.125.11.2099

78. Fernández-Llebrez P, Pérez J, Nadales AE, Cifuentes M, Grondona JM, Mancera JM, et al. Immunocytochemical study of the hypothalamic magnocellular neurosecretory nuclei of the snake *Natrix maura* and the turtle *Mauremys caspica*. *Cell Tissue Res.* 1988;253(2):435-445. DOI: 10.1007/BF00222301
79. Ferran JL, Puellas L, Rubenstein JL. Molecular codes defining rostrocaudal domains in the embryonic mouse hypothalamus. *Front Neuroanat.* 2015 Apr;9:46. DOI: 10.3389/fnana.2015.00046
80. Foidart A, Lakaye B, Grisar T, Ball GF, Balthazart J. Estrogen receptor-beta in quail: cloning, tissue expression and neuroanatomical distribution. *J Neurobiol.* 1999;40(3):327-342.
81. Gadziola MA, Grimsley JM, Shanbhag SJ, Wenstrup JJ. A novel coding mechanism for social vocalizations in the lateral amygdala. *J Neurophysiol.* 2012;107(4):1047-1057. DOI: 10.1152/jn.00422.2011
82. Gao R, Penzes P. Common mechanisms of excitatory and inhibitory imbalance in schizophrenia and autism spectrum disorders. *Curr Mol Med.* 2015;15(2):146-167. DOI: 10.2174/1566524015666150303003028
83. García-Calero E, Martínez-de-la-Torre M, Puellas L. A radial histogenetic model of the mouse pallial amygdala. *Brain Struct Funct.* 2020;225(7):1921-1956. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-020-02097-4
84. García-Calero E, Puellas L. Development of the mouse anterior amygdalar radial unit marked by Lhx9-expression. *Brain Struct Funct.* 2021;226(2):575-600. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-020-02201-8
85. García-López M, Abellán A, Legaz I, Rubenstein JL, Puellas L, Medina L. Histogenetic compartments of the mouse centromedial and extended amygdala based on gene expression patterns during development. *J Comp Neurol.* 2008;506(1):46-74. DOI: 10.1002/cne.21524
86. García-Moreno F, Molnár Z. Variations of telencephalic development that paved the way for neocortical evolution. *Prog Neurobiol.* 2020;194:101865. DOI: 10.1016/j.pneurobio.2020.101865
87. García-Moreno F, Pedraza M, Di Giovannantonio LG, Di Salvio M, López-Mascaraque L, Simeone A, et al. A neuronal migratory pathway crossing from diencephalon to telencephalon populates amygdala nuclei. *Nat Neurosci.* 2010;13(6):680-689. DOI: 10.1038/nn.2556
88. García-Moreno F, Anderton E, Jankowska M, Begbie J, Encinas JM, Irimia M, et al. Absence of Tangentially Migrating Glutamatergic Neurons in the Developing Avian Brain. *Cell Rep.* 2018;22(1):96-109. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2017.12.032

89. Gedman G, Haase B, Durieux G, Biegler MT, Fedrigo O, Jarvis ED. As above, so below: Whole transcriptome profiling demonstrates strong molecular similarities between avian dorsal and ventral pallial subdivisions. *J Comp Neurol.* 2021;529(12):3222-3246. DOI: 10.1002/cne.25159
90. González A, Morona R, Moreno N, Bandín S, López JM. Identification of striatal and pallidal regions in the subpallium of anamniotes. *Brain Behav Evol.* 2014;83(2):93-103. DOI: 10.1159/000357754
91. Goodson JL. The vertebrate social behavior network: evolutionary themes and variations. *Horm Behav.* 2005;48(1):11-22. DOI: 10.1016/j.yhbeh.2005.02.003
92. Grassi D, Marraudino M, Garcia-Segura LM, Panzica GC. The hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus as a central hub for the estrogenic modulation of neuroendocrine function and behavior. *Front Neuroendocrinol.* 2022;65:100974. DOI: 10.1016/j.yfrne.2021.100974
93. Gray TS. Amygdaloid CRF pathways. Role in autonomic, neuroendocrine, and behavioral responses to stress. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 1993;697:53-60. DOI: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.1993.tb49922.x
94. Gray TS, Magnuson DJ. Peptide immunoreactive neurons in the amygdala and the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis project to the midbrain central gray in the rat. *Peptides.* 1992;13(3):451-460. DOI: 10.1016/0196-9781(92)90074-d
95. Grossmann R, Jurkevich A, Köhler A. Sex dimorphism in the avian arginine vasotocin system with special emphasis to the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis. *Comp Biochem Physiol A Mol Integr Physiol.* 2002;131(4):833-837. DOI: 10.1016/s1095-6433(02)00021-1
96. Güntürkün O. The avian 'prefrontal cortex' and cognition. *Curr Opin Neurobiol.* 2005;15(6):686-693. DOI: 10.1016/j.conb.2005.10.003
97. Halpern M, Martínez-Marcos A. Structure and function of the vomeronasal system: an update. *Prog Neurobiol.* 2003;70(3):245-318. DOI: 10.1016/s0301-0082(03)00103-5
98. Han TM, De Vries GJ. Organizational effects of testosterone, estradiol, and dihydrotestosterone on vasopressin mRNA expression in the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis. *J Neurobiol.* 2003;54(3):502-510. DOI: 10.1002/neu.10157
99. Hanics J, Teleki G, Alpár A, Székely AD, Csillag A. Multiple amygdaloid divisions of arcopallium send convergent projections to the nucleus accumbens and neighboring subpallial amygdala regions in the domestic chicken: a selective pathway tracing and reconstruction study. *Brain Struct Funct.* 2017;222(1):301-315. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-016-1219-8

100. Haubensak W, Kunwar PS, Cai H, Cioocchi S, Wall NR, Ponnusamy R, et al. Genetic dissection of an amygdala microcircuit that gates conditioned fear. *Nature*. 2010;468(7321):270-276. DOI: 10.1038/nature09553
101. Heimer L. A new anatomical framework for neuropsychiatric disorders and drug abuse [published correction appears in *Am J Psychiatry*. 2003 Dec;160(12):2258]. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2003;160(10):1726-1739. DOI: 10.1176/appi.ajp.160.10.1726
102. Hevner RF, Shi L, Justice N, et al. Tbr1 regulates differentiation of the preplate and layer 6. *Neuron*. 2001;29(2):353-366. DOI: 10.1016/s0896-6273(01)00211-2
103. Hirata T, Li P, Lanuza GM, Cocas LA, Huntsman MM, Corbin JG. Identification of distinct telencephalic progenitor pools for neuronal diversity in the amygdala. *Nat Neurosci*. 2009;12(2):141-149. DOI: 10.1038/nn.2241
104. Hong W, Kim DW, Anderson DJ. Antagonistic control of social versus repetitive self-grooming behaviors by separable amygdala neuronal subsets. *Cell*. 2014;158(6):1348-1361. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2014.07.049
105. Jarvis ED, Güntürkün O, Bruce L, Csillag A, Karten H, Kuenzel W, et al. Avian brains and a new understanding of vertebrate brain evolution. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2005;6(2):151-159. DOI: 10.1038/nrn1606
106. Jarvis ED, Yu J, Rivas MV, Horita H, Feenders G, Whitney O, et al. Global view of the functional molecular organization of the avian cerebrum: mirror images and functional columns. *J Comp Neurol*. 2013;521(16):3614-3665. DOI: 10.1002/cne.23404
107. Jarvis ED, Mirarab S, Aberer AJ, Li B, Houde P, Li C, et al. Whole-genome analyses resolve early branches in the tree of life of modern birds. *Science*. 2014;346(6215):1320-1331. DOI: 10.1126/science.1253451
108. Jiménez S, Moreno N. Analysis of the Pallial Amygdala in Anurans: Derivatives and Cellular Components. *Brain Behav Evol*. 2022. DOI: 10.1159/000525018.
109. Johnson CS, Hong W, Micevych PE. Posterodorsal Medial Amygdala Regulation of Female Social Behavior: GABA versus Glutamate Projections. *J Neurosci*. 2021;41(42):8790-8800. DOI: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1103-21.2021
110. Jurkevich A, Barth SW, Kuenzel WJ, Köhler A, Grossmann R. Development of sexually dimorphic vasotocinergic system in the bed nucleus of stria terminalis in chickens. *J Comp Neurol*. 1999;408(1):46-60. DOI: 10.1002/(sici)1096-9861(19990524)408:1<46::aid-cne4>3.0.co;2-5

111. Kabelik D, Julien AR, Ramirez D, O'Connell LA. Social boldness correlates with brain gene expression in male green anoles. *Horm Behav.* 2021;133:105007. DOI: 10.1016/j.yhbeh.2021.105007
112. Kabelik D, Julien AR, Waddell BR, Batschelett MA, O'Connell LA. Aggressive but not reproductive boldness in male green anole lizards correlates with baseline vasopressin activity. *Horm Behav.* 2022;140:105109. DOI: 10.1016/j.yhbeh.2022.105109
113. Kaoru T, Liu FC, Ishida M, Oishi T, Hayashi M, Kitagawa M, et al. Molecular characterization of the intercalated cell masses of the amygdala: implications for the relationship with the striatum. *Neuroscience.* 2010;166(1):220-230. DOI: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2009.12.004
114. Karten HJ. Evolutionary developmental biology meets the brain: the origins of mammalian cortex. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 1997;94(7):2800-2804. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.94.7.2800
115. Kelly AM, Goodson JL. Hypothalamic oxytocin and vasopressin neurons exert sex-specific effects on pair bonding, gregariousness, and aggression in finches. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2014;111(16):6069-6074. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1322554111
116. Kiss J, Csáki A, Halász B. Location of glutamatergic/aspartatergic neurons projecting to the hypothalamic ventromedial nucleus studied by autoradiography of retrogradely transported [³H]D-aspartate. *Neuroscience.* 2011;176:210-224. DOI: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2010.12.047
117. Klein S, Jurkevich A, Grossmann R. Sexually dimorphic immunoreactivity of galanin and colocalization with arginine vasotocin in the chicken brain (*Gallus gallus domesticus*). *J Comp Neurol.* 2006;499(5):828-839. DOI: 10.1002/cne.21132
118. Kröner S, Güntürkün O. Afferent and efferent connections of the caudolateral neostriatum in the pigeon (*Columba livia*): a retro- and anterograde pathway tracing study. *J Comp Neurol.* 1999;407(2):228-260. DOI: 10.1002/(sici)1096-9861(19990503)407:2<228::aid-cne6>3.0.co;2-2
119. Kuenzel WJ, Jurkevich A. Molecular neuroendocrine events during stress in poultry. *Poult Sci.* 2010;89(4):832-840. DOI: 10.3382/ps.2009-00376
120. Kuenzel WJ, Beck MM, Teruyama R. Neural sites and pathways regulating food intake in birds: a comparative analysis to mammalian systems. *J Exp Zool.* 1999;283(4-5):348-364. DOI: 10.1002/(sici)1097-010x(19990301/01)283:4/5<348::aid-jez5>3.0.co;2-5
121. Kuenzel WJ, Medina L, Csillag A, Perkel DJ, Reiner A. The avian subpallium: new insights into structural and functional subdivisions occupying the lateral subpallial wall and their embryological origins. *Brain Res.* 2011;1424:67-101. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainres.2011.09.037

122. Lanuza E, Font C, Martínez-Marcos A, Martínez-García F. Amygdalo-hypothalamic projections in the lizard *Podarcis hispanica*: a combined anterograde and retrograde tracing study. *J Comp Neurol.* 1997;384(4):537-555. DOI: 10.1002/(sici)1096-9861(19970811)384:4<537::aid-cne4>3.0.co;2-3
123. Lanuza E, Belekova M, Martínez-Marcos A, Font C, Martínez-García F. Identification of the reptilian basolateral amygdala: an anatomical investigation of the afferents to the posterior dorsal ventricular ridge of the lizard *Podarcis hispanica*. *Eur J Neurosci.* 1998;10(11):3517-3534. DOI: 10.1046/j.1460-9568.1998.00363.x
124. Le TN, Zhou QP, Cobos I, Zhang S, Zagozewski J, Japoni S, et al. GABAergic Interneuron Differentiation in the Basal Forebrain Is Mediated through Direct Regulation of Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase Isoforms by Dlx Homeobox Transcription Factors. *J Neurosci.* 2017;37(36):8816-8829. DOI: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2125-16.2017
125. Lindtner S, Catta-Preta R, Tian H, Su-Feher L, Price JD, Dickel DE, et al. Genomic Resolution of DLX-Orchestrated Transcriptional Circuits Driving Development of Forebrain GABAergic Neurons. *Cell Rep.* 2019;28(8):2048-2063.e8. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2019.07.022
126. Lischinsky JE, Sokolowski K, Li P, Esumi S, Kamal Y, Goodrich M, et al. Embryonic transcription factor expression in mice predicts medial amygdala neuronal identity and sex-specific responses to innate behavioral cues. *Elife.* 2017 Mar;6:e21012. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.21012
127. López JM, Jiménez S, Morona R, Lozano D, Moreno N. Analysis of *Islet-1*, *Nkx2.1*, *Pax6*, and *Orthopedia* in the forebrain of the sturgeon *Acipenser ruthenus* identifies conserved prosomeric characteristics. *J Comp Neurol.* 2022;530(5):834-855. DOI: 10.1002/cne.25249
128. López-Avalos MD, Mancera JM, Pérez-Fígares JM, Fernández-Llebrez P. Immunocytochemical localization of corticotropin-releasing factor in the brain of the turtle, *Mauremys caspica*. *Anat Embryol (Berl).* 1993;188(2):163-171. DOI: 10.1007/BF00186250
129. Ma J, Kanwal JS. Stimulation of the basal and central amygdala in the mustached bat triggers echolocation and agonistic vocalizations within multimodal output. *Front Physiol.* 2014 Mar;5:55. DOI: 10.3389/fphys.2014.00055
130. Mancera JM, López-Avalos MD, Pérez-Fígares JM, Fernández-Llebrez P. The distribution of corticotropin-releasing factor--immunoreactive neurons and nerve fibers in the brain of the snake, *Natrix maura*. Coexistence with arginine vasotocin and mesotocin. *Cell Tissue Res.* 1991;264(3):539-548. DOI: 10.1007/BF00319043

131. Martínez-García F, Olucha FE, Teruel V, Lorente MJ, Schwerdtfeger WK. Afferent and efferent connections of the olfactory bulbs in the lizard *Podarcis hispanica*. *J Comp Neurol*. 1991;305(2):337-347. DOI: 10.1002/cne.903050214
132. Martínez-García F, Martínez-Marcos A, Lanuza E. The pallial amygdala of amniote vertebrates: evolution of the concept, evolution of the structure. *Brain Res Bull*. 2002 Feb-Mar; 57(3-4):463–9.
133. Martínez-García F, Novejarque A, Lanuza E. Evolution of the amygdala in vertebrates. In: Kass JH, editor. *Evolution of Nervous Systems. A Comprehensive Reference*. Oxford: Elsevier- Academic Press; 2007. Vol. 2, p. 255–334.
134. Martínez-García F, Novejarque A, Lanuza E. Two interconnected functional systems in the amygdala of amniote vertebrates. *Brain Res Bull*. 2008;75(2-4):206-213. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainresbull.2007.10.019
135. Martínez-García F, Novejarque A, Gutiérrez-Castellanos N, Lanuza E (2012) Piriform cortex and amygdala. In: GP Charles Watson, George Paxinos, Luis Puelles, Charles Watson, L Puelles (eds) *The mouse nervous system*, pp 140–172. Academic Press, San Diego.
<http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780123694973100068>
136. Mayer U, Rosa-Salva O, Vallortigara G. First exposure to an alive conspecific activates septal and amygdaloid nuclei in visually-naïve domestic chicks (*Gallus gallus*). *Behav Brain Res*. 2017;317:71-81. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbr.2016.09.031
137. McCullough KM, Morrison FG, Hartmann J, Carlezon WA Jr, Ressler KJ. Quantified Coexpression Analysis of Central Amygdala Subpopulations. *eNeuro*. 2018 Feb;5(1):ENEURO.0010-18.2018. DOI: 10.1523/ENEURO.0010-18.2018
138. McDonald AJ. Somatostatinergic projections from the amygdala to the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis and medial preoptic-hypothalamic region. *Neurosci Lett*. 1987;75(3):271-277. DOI: 10.1016/0304-3940(87)90533-7
139. McDonald AJ, Shammah-Lagnado SJ, Shi C, Davis M. Cortical afferents to the extended amygdala. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 1999;877:309-338. DOI: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.1999.tb09275.x
140. Medina L. Field homologies. In: Kaas JH, Striedter GF, Rubenstein JLR, editors. *Evolution of nervous systems: a comprehensive reference*. Amsterdam: Academic Press-Elsevier; 2007. Vol. 1: Theories, development, invertebrates, p. 73–87. DOI: 10.1016/B0-12-370878-8/00097-5.
141. Medina L, Abellán A. Development and evolution of the pallium. *Semin Cell Dev Biol*. 2009;20(6):698-711. DOI: 10.1016/j.semcdb.2009.04.008

142. Medina L, Abellán A, Desfilis E. A never-ending search for the evolutionary origin of the neocortex: rethinking the homology concept. *Brain Behav Evol.* 2013;81(3):150-153. DOI: 10.1159/000348282
143. Medina L, Abellán A, Desfilis E. Evolution of pallial areas and networks involved in sociality: comparison between mammals and sauropsids. *Front Physiol.* 2019 Jul;10:894.
144. Medina L, Abellán A, Desfilis E. Evolving Views on the Pallium. *Brain Behav Evol.* 2022;96(4-6):181-199. DOI: 10.1159/000519260
145. Medina L, Abellán A, Vicario A, Castro-Robles B, Desfilis E. The amygdala. In: Kaas JH, editor. *Evolution of nervous systems.* 2nd ed. Oxford: Elsevier; 2017. Vol. 1, p. 427–78.
146. Medina L, Bupesh M, Abellán A. Contribution of genoarchitecture to understanding forebrain evolution and development, with particular emphasis on the amygdala. *Brain Behav Evol.* 2011;78(3):216–36.
147. Medina L, Legaz I, González G, De Castro F, Rubenstein JL, Puelles L. Expression of Dbx1, Neurogenin 2, Semaphorin 5A, Cadherin 8, and Emx1 distinguish ventral and lateral pallial histogenetic divisions in the developing mouse claustramygdaloid complex. *J Comp Neurol.* 2004 Jul;474(4):504–23.
148. Metwalli AH, Abellán A, Freixes J, Pross A, Desfilis E, Medina L. Distinct Subdivisions in the Transition Between Telencephalon and Hypothalamus Produce Otp and Sim1 Cells for the Extended Amygdala in Sauropsids. *Front Neuroanat.* 2022 May;16:883537. DOI: 10.3389/fnana.2022.883537
149. Moczek AP, Sears KE, Stollewerk A, Wittkopp PJ, Diggie P, Dworkin J, et al. The significance and scope of evolutionary developmental biology: a vision for the 21st century. *Evol Dev.* 2015;17(3):198-219. DOI: 10.1111/ede.12125
150. Moga MM, Gray TS. Evidence for corticotropin-releasing factor, neurotensin, and somatostatin in the neural pathway from the central nucleus of the amygdala to the parabrachial nucleus. *J Comp Neurol.* 1985;241(3):275-284. DOI: 10.1002/cne.902410304
151. Moga MM, Saper CB, Gray TS. Bed nucleus of the stria terminalis: cytoarchitecture, immunohistochemistry, and projection to the parabrachial nucleus in the rat. *J Comp Neurol.* 1989;283(3):315-332. DOI: 10.1002/cne.902830302
152. Morales L, Castro-Robles B, Abellán A, Desfilis E, Medina L. A novel telencephalon-opto-hypothalamic morphogenetic domain coexpressing Foxg1 and Otp produces most of the

glutamatergic neurons of the medial extended amygdala. *J Comp Neurol.* 2021;529(10):2418-2449. DOI: 10.1002/cne.25103

153. Morales L, González-Alonso A, Desfilis E, Medina L. Precise Mapping of Otp Expressing Cells Across Different Pallial Regions Throughout Ontogenesis Using Otp-Specific Reporter Transgenic Mice. *Front Neural Circuits.* 2022 Feb;16:831074. DOI: 10.3389/fncir.2022.831074

154. Morales-Delgado N, Merchan P, Bardet SM, Ferrán JL, Puelles L, Díaz C. Topography of Somatostatin Gene Expression Relative to Molecular Progenitor Domains during Ontogeny of the Mouse Hypothalamus. *Front Neuroanat.* 2011 Feb;5:10. DOI: 10.3389/fnana.2011.00010

155. Moreau MX, Saillour Y, Cwetsch AW, Pierani A, Causeret F. Single-cell transcriptomics of the early developing mouse cerebral cortex disentangle the spatial and temporal components of neuronal fate acquisition. *Development.* 2021 Jul;148(14):dev197962. DOI: 10.1242/dev.197962.

156. Moreno N, González A. The common organization of the amygdaloid complex in tetrapods: new concepts based on developmental, hodological and neurochemical data in anuran amphibians. *Prog Neurobiol.* 2006;78(2):61-90. DOI: 10.1016/j.pneurobio.2005.12.005

157. Moreno N, Bachy I, Rétaux S, González A. LIM-homeodomain genes as developmental and adult genetic markers of *Xenopus* forebrain functional subdivisions. *J Comp Neurol.* 2004;472(1):52-72. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20046

158. Moreno N, González A, Rétaux S. Development and evolution of the subpallium. *Semin Cell Dev Biol.* 2009 Aug;20(6):735-43. DOI: 10.1016/j.semcdb.2009.04.007.

159. Moreno N, Morona R, López JM, González A. Subdivisions of the turtle *Pseudemys scripta* subpallium based on the expression of regulatory genes and neuronal markers. *J Comp Neurol.* 2010;518(24):4877-4902. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22493

160. Moreno N, Domínguez L, Morona R, González A. Subdivisions of the turtle *Pseudemys scripta* hypothalamus based on the expression of regulatory genes and neuronal markers. *J Comp Neurol.* 2012;520(3):453-478. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22762

161. Moreno N, López JM, Morona R, Lozano D, Jiménez S, González A. Comparative Analysis of Nkx2.1 and Islet-1 Expression in Urodele Amphibians and Lungfishes Highlights the Pattern of Forebrain Organization in Early Tetrapods. *Front Neuroanat.* 2018 May;12:42. DOI: 10.3389/fnana.2018.00042

162. Morris JA, Jordan CL, King ZA, Northcutt KV, Breedlove SM. Sexual dimorphism and steroid responsiveness of the posterodorsal medial amygdala in adult mice. *Brain Res.* 2008;1190:115-121. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainres.2007.11.005
163. Moscarello JM, Penzo MA. The central nucleus of the amygdala and the construction of defensive modes across the threat-imminence continuum. *Nat Neurosci.* 2022;25(8):999-1008. DOI: 10.1038/s41593-022-01130-5
164. Mueller T. The Everted Amygdala of Ray-Finned Fish: Zebrafish Makes a Case. *Brain Behav Evol.* 2022. DOI:10.1159/000525669
165. Murakami Y, Ogasawara M, Sugahara F, Hirano S, Satoh N, Kuratani S. Identification and expression of the lamprey Pax6 gene: evolutionary origin of the segmented brain of vertebrates. *Development.* 2001;128(18):3521-3531. DOI: 10.1242/dev.128.18.3521
166. Nagarajan G, Tessaro BA, Kang SW, Kuenzel WJ. Identification of arginine vasotocin (AVT) neurons activated by acute and chronic restraint stress in the avian septum and anterior diencephalon. *Gen Comp Endocrinol.* 2014;202:59-68. DOI: 10.1016/j.ygcen.2014.04.012
167. Newman SW. The medial extended amygdala in male reproductive behavior. A node in the mammalian social behavior network. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 1999;877:242-257. DOI: 10.1111/j.17496632.1999.tb09271.x
168. Nieuwenhuys R. Comparative Neuroanatomy: Place, Principles and Programme. In: Nieuwenhuys R, ten Donkelaar HJ, Nicholson C, editors. *The Central Nervous System of Vertebrates.* Berlin: Springer; 1998. Vol. 1, p. 273–326.
169. Nieuwenhuys R, Puelles L. *Towards a New Neuromorphology.* Heidelberg: Springer; 2016. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-25693-1.
170. Novejarque A, Lanuza E, Martínez-García F. Amygdalostriatal projections in reptiles: a tract-tracing study in the lizard *Podarcis hispanica*. *J Comp Neurol.* 2004;479(3):287-308. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20309
171. O'Connell LA, Hofmann HA. Genes, hormones, and circuits: an integrative approach to study the evolution of social behavior. *Front Neuroendocrinol.* 2011;32(3):320-335. DOI: 10.1016/j.yfrne.2010.12.004
172. Osório J, Mueller T, Rétaux S, Vernier P, Wullimann MF. Phylotypic expression of the bHLH genes *Neurogenin2*, *Neurod*, and *Mash1* in the mouse embryonic forebrain. *J Comp Neurol.* 2010;518(6):851-871. DOI: 10.1002/cne.22247

173. Otero-García M, Martin-Sanchez A, Fortes-Marco L, Martínez-Ricós J, Agustín-Pavón C, Lanuza E, et al. Extending the socio-sexual brain: arginine-vasopressin immunoreactive circuits in the telencephalon of mice. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2014;219(3):1055-1081. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-013-0553-3
174. Otero-García M, Agustín-Pavón C, Lanuza E, Martínez-García F. Distribution of oxytocin and co-localization with arginine vasopressin in the brain of mice. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2016;221(7):3445-3473. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-015-1111-y
175. Panzica GC, Viglietti-Panzica C, Fasolo A, Vandesande F. CRF-like immunoreactive system in the quail brain. *J Hirnforsch*. 1986;27(5):539-547.
176. Panzica GC, Viglietti-Panzica C, Balthazart J. The sexually dimorphic medial preoptic nucleus of quail: a key brain area mediating steroid action on male sexual behavior. *Front Neuroendocrinol*. 1996;17(1):51-125. DOI: 10.1006/frne.1996.0002
177. Panzica GC, Aste N, Castagna C, Viglietti-Panzica C, Balthazart J. Steroid-induced plasticity in the sexually dimorphic vasotocinergic innervation of the avian brain: behavioral implications. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev*. 2001a;37(1-3):178-200. DOI: 10.1016/s0165-0173(01)00118-7
178. Panzica G, Viglietti-Panzica C, Balthazart J. Sexual dimorphism in the neuronal circuits of the quail preoptic and limbic regions. *Microsc Res Tech*. 2001b;54(6):364-374. DOI: 10.1002/jemt.1149
179. Pare D, Duvarci S. Amygdala microcircuits mediating fear expression and extinction. *Curr Opin Neurobiol*. 2012;22(4):717-723. DOI: 10.1016/j.conb.2012.02.014
180. Penzo MA, Robert V, Li B. Fear conditioning potentiates synaptic transmission onto long-range projection neurons in the lateral subdivision of central amygdala. *J Neurosci*. 2014;34(7):2432-2437. DOI: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.4166-13.2014
181. Pessoa L, Medina L, Hof PR, Desfilis E. Neural architecture of the vertebrate brain: implications for the interaction between emotion and cognition. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*. 2019;107:296-312. DOI: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2019.09.021
182. Peter IS, Davidson EH. Evolution of gene regulatory networks controlling body plan development. *Cell*. 2011;144(6):970-985. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2011.02.017
183. Pfenning AR, Hara E, Whitney O, Rivas MV, Wang R, Roulhac PL, et al. Convergent transcriptional specializations in the brains of humans and song-learning birds. *Science*. 2014;346(6215):1256846. DOI: 10.1126/science.1256846
184. Phelps EA, LeDoux JE. Contributions of the amygdala to emotion processing: from animal models to human behavior. *Neuron*. 2005;48(2):175-187. DOI: 10.1016/j.neuron.2005.09.025

185. Planas B, Kolb PE, Raskind MA, Miller MA. Galanin in the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis and medial amygdala of the rat: lack of sexual dimorphism despite regulation of gene expression across puberty. *Endocrinology*. 1994;134(5):1999-2004. DOI: 10.1210/endo.134.5.7512493
186. Planas B, Kolb PE, Raskind MA, Miller MA. Sex difference in coexpression by galanin neurons accounts for sexual dimorphism of vasopressin in the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis. *Endocrinology*. 1995;136(2):727-733. DOI: 10.1210/endo.136.2.7530652
187. Porter BA, Mueller T. The Zebrafish Amygdaloid Complex - Functional Ground Plan, Molecular Delineation, and Everted Topology. *Front Neurosci*. 2020 Jul;14:608. DOI: 10.3389/fnins.2020.00608
188. Poulin JF, Chevalier B, Laforest S, Drolet G. Enkephalinergic afferents of the centromedial amygdala in the rat. *J Comp Neurol*. 2006;496(6):859-876. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20956
189. Pross A, Metwalli AH, Desfilis E, Medina L. Developmental-Based Classification of Enkephalin and Somatostatin Containing Neurons of the Chicken Central Extended Amygdala. *Front Physiol* 2022 May;13. DOI: 10.3389/fphys.2022.904520
190. Puelles L. Thoughts on the development, structure and evolution of the mammalian and avian telencephalic pallium. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*. 2001;356(1414):1583-1598. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2001.0973
191. Puelles L. Comments on the Updated Tetrapartite Pallium Model in the Mouse and Chick, Featuring a Homologous Claustro-Insular Complex. *Brain Behav Evol*. 2017;90(2):171-189. DOI: 10.1159/000479782
192. Puelles L, Medina L. Field homology as a way to reconcile genetic and developmental variability with adult homology. *Brain Res Bull*. 2002;57(3-4):243-255. DOI: 10.1016/s0361-9230(01)00693-1
193. Puelles L, Morales-Delgado N, Merchán P, Castro-Robles B, Martínez-de-la-Torre M, Díaz C, et al. Radial and tangential migration of telencephalic somatostatin neurons originated from the mouse diagonal area. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2016;221(6):3027-3065. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-015-1086-8
194. Puelles L, Kuwana E, Puelles E, Bulfone A, Shimamura K, Keleher J, et al. Pallial and subpallial derivatives in the embryonic chick and mouse telencephalon, traced by the expression of the genes *Dlx-2*, *Emx-1*, *Nkx-2.1*, *Pax-6*, and *Tbr-1*. *J Comp Neurol*. 2000;424(3):409-438. DOI: 10.1002/1096-9861(20000828)424:3<409::aid-cne3>3.0.co;2-7
195. Puelles L, Alonso A, García-Calero E, Martínez-de-la-Torre M. Concentric ring topology of mammalian cortical sectors and relevance for patterning studies. *J Comp Neurol*. 2019;527(10):1731-1752. DOI: 10.1002/cne.24650

196. Rao ZR, Yamano M, Shiosaka S, Shinohara A, Tohyama M. Origin of leucine-enkephalin fibers and their two main afferent pathways in the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis in the rat. *Exp Brain Res.* 1987;65(2):411-420. DOI: 10.1007/BF00236314
197. Rasri K, Mason P, Govitrapong P, Pevet P, Klosen P. Testosterone-driven seasonal regulation of vasopressin and galanin in the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis of the Djungarian hamster (*Phodopus sungorus*). *Neuroscience.* 2008;157(1):174-187. DOI: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2008.08.058
198. Real MA, Heredia R, Labrador Mdel C, Dávila JC, Guirado S. Expression of somatostatin and neuropeptide Y in the embryonic, postnatal, and adult mouse amygdalar complex. *J Comp Neurol.* 2009;513(4):335-348. DOI: 10.1002/cne.21970
199. Redies C, Medina L, Puelles L. Cadherin expression by embryonic divisions and derived gray matter structures in the telencephalon of the chicken. *J Comp Neurol.* 2001;438(3):253-285.
200. Reiner A. The distribution of proenkephalin-derived peptides in the central nervous system of turtles. *J Comp Neurol.* 1987;259(1):65-91. DOI: 10.1002/cne.902590106
201. Reiner A. A comparison of neurotransmitter-specific and neuropeptide-specific neuronal cell types present in the dorsal cortex in turtles with those present in the isocortex in mammals: implications for the evolution of isocortex. *Brain Behav Evol.* 1991;38(2-3):53-91. DOI: 10.1159/000114379
202. Reiner A. Neurotransmitter organization and connections of turtle cortex: implications for the evolution of mammalian isocortex. *Comp Biochem Physiol Comp Physiol.* 1993;104(4):735-748. DOI: 10.1016/0300-9629(93)90149-x
203. Reiner A, Karten HJ. Comparison of olfactory bulb projections in pigeons and turtles. *Brain Behav Evol.* 1985;27(1):11-27. DOI: 10.1159/000118717
204. Reiner A, Krause JE, Keyser KT, Eldred WD, McKelvy JF. The distribution of substance P in turtle nervous system: a radioimmunoassay and immunohistochemical study. *J Comp Neurol.* 1984;226(1):50-75. DOI: 10.1002/cne.902260105
205. Reiner A, Perkel DJ, Bruce LL, Butler AB, Csillag A, Kuenzel W, et al. Revised nomenclature for avian telencephalon and some related brainstem nuclei [published correction appears in *J Comp Neurol.* 2004 Jul 19;475(2):288. Gütürkün, Onur [corrected to Gütürkün, Onur]]. *J Comp Neurol.* 2004;473(3):377-414. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20118

206. Richard S, Martínez-García F, Lanuza E, Davies DC. Distribution of corticotropin-releasing factor-immunoreactive neurons in the central nervous system of the domestic chicken and Japanese quail. *J Comp Neurol.* 2004;469(4):559-580. DOI: 10.1002/cne.11023
207. Ritters LV, Pawlisch BA. Evidence that norepinephrine influences responses to male courtship song and activity within song control regions and the ventromedial nucleus of the hypothalamus in female European starlings. *Brain Res.* 2007;1149:127-140. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainres.2007.02.059
208. Rodríguez-Moldes I, Quintana-Urzaínqui I, Santos-Durán GN, Ferreiro-Galve S, Pereira-Guldrís S, Candás M, et al. Identifying Amygdala-Like Territories in *Scyliorhinus canicula* (Chondrichthyan): Evidence for a Pallial Amygdala. *Brain Behav Evol.* 2021;96(4-6):283-304. DOI: 10.1159/000519221
209. Ruiz-Reig N, Studer M. Rostro-Caudal and Caudo-Rostral Migrations in the Telencephalon: Going Forward or Backward?. *Front Neurosci.* 2017 Dec;11:692. DOI: 10.3389/fnins.2017.00692
210. Ruiz-Reig N, Andrés B, Huilgol D, Grove EA, Tissir F, Tole S, et al. Lateral Thalamic Eminence: A Novel Origin for mGluR1/Lot Cells. *Cereb Cortex.* 2017;27(5):2841-2856. DOI: 10.1093/cercor/bhw126
211. Saint-Dizier H, Constantin P, Davies DC, Leterrier C, Lévy F, Richard S. Subdivisions of the arcopallium/posterior pallial amygdala complex are differentially involved in the control of fear behaviour in the Japanese quail. *Brain Res Bull.* 2009;79(5):288-295. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainresbull.2009.03.004
212. Silveira PF, Breno MC, Puerto G, Martín del Río MP, Mancera JM. Corticotropin-releasing hormone-like immunoreactivity in the brain of the snake *Bothrops jararaca*. *Histochem J.* 2001;33(11-12):685-694. DOI: 10.1023/a:1016362603722
213. Smeets WJ, Alonso JR, González A. Distribution of NADPH-diaphorase and nitric oxide synthase in relation to catecholaminergic neuronal structures in the brain of the lizard *Gekko gekko*. *J Comp Neurol.* 1997;377(1):121-141.
214. Smulders TV. Telencephalic regulation of the HPA axis in birds. *Neurobiol Stress.* 2021 Jun;15:100351. DOI: 10.1016/j.ynstr.2021.100351
215. Sohal VS, Rubenstein JLR. Excitation-inhibition balance as a framework for investigating mechanisms in neuropsychiatric disorders. *Mol Psychiatry.* 2019;24(9):1248-1257. DOI: 10.1038/s41380-019-0426-0
216. Sokolowski K, Corbin JG. Wired for behaviors: from development to function of innate limbic system circuitry. *Front Mol Neurosci.* 2012 Apr;5:55. DOI: 10.3389/fnmol.2012.00055

217. Striedter GF. The vocal control pathways in budgerigars differ from those in songbirds. *J Comp Neurol.* 1994;343(1):35-56. DOI: 10.1002/cne.903430104
218. Striedter GF. The telencephalon of tetrapods in evolution. *Brain Behav Evol.* 1997;49(4):179-213. DOI: 10.1159/000112991
219. Striedter GF. Stepping into the same river twice: homologues as recurring attractors in epigenetic landscapes. *Brain Behav Evol.* 1998;52(4-5):218-231. DOI: 10.1159/000006565
220. Striedter GF. Homology in the nervous system: of characters, embryology and levels of analysis. *Novartis Found Symp.* 1999;222:158-172. DOI: 10.1002/9780470515655.ch11
221. Striedter GF, Northcutt RG. Biological hierarchies and the concept of homology. *Brain Behav Evol.* 1991;38(4-5):177-189. DOI: 10.1159/000114387
222. Striedter GF, Northcutt RG. *Brains through time: A natural history of vertebrates.* New York: Oxford University Press; 2020.
223. Stühmer T, Anderson SA, Ekker M, Rubenstein JL. Ectopic expression of the *Dlx* genes induces glutamic acid decarboxylase and *Dlx* expression. *Development.* 2002;129(1):245-252. DOI: 10.1242/dev.129.1.245
224. Sugahara F, Murakami Y, Pascual-Anaya J, Kuratani S. Reconstructing the ancestral vertebrate brain. *Dev Growth Differ.* 2017;59(4):163-174. DOI: 10.1111/dgd.12347
225. Swanson LW. Cerebral hemisphere regulation of motivated behavior. *Brain Res.* 2000;886(1-2):113-164. DOI: 10.1016/s0006-8993(00)02905-x
226. Swanson LW, Petrovich GD. What is the amygdala?. *Trends Neurosci.* 1998;21(8):323-331. DOI: 10.1016/s0166-2236(98)01265-x
227. Tanaka M, Ikeda T, Hayashi S, Iijima N, Amaya F, Hisa Y, et al. Nitroergic neurons in the medial amygdala project to the hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus of the rat. *Brain Res.* 1997;777(1-2):13-21. DOI: 10.1016/s0006-8993(97)00948-7
228. Tang K, Rubenstein JL, Tsai SY, Tsai MJ. COUP-TFII controls amygdala patterning by regulating neuropilin expression. *Development.* 2012;139(9):1630-1639. DOI: 10.1242/dev.075564
229. Todd RM, Anderson AK. Six degrees of separation: the amygdala regulates social behavior and perception. *Nat Neurosci.* 2009;12(10):1217-1218. DOI: 10.1038/nn1009-1217

230. Tokarev K, Tiunova A, Scharff C, Anokhin K. Food for song: expression of c-Fos and ZENK in the zebra finch song nuclei during food aversion learning. *PLoS One*. 2011;6(6):e21157. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0021157
231. Tosches MA, Yamawaki TM, Naumann RK, Jacobi AA, Tushev G, Laurent G. Evolution of pallium, hippocampus, and cortical cell types revealed by single-cell transcriptomics in reptiles. *Science*. 2018;360(6391):881-888. DOI: 10.1126/science.aar4237
232. Tye KM, Prakash R, Kim SY, Fenno LE, Grosenick L, Zarabi H, et al. Amygdala circuitry mediating reversible and bidirectional control of anxiety. *Nature*. 2011;471(7338):358-362. DOI: 10.1038/nature09820
233. Ulrich-Lai YM, Herman JP. Neural regulation of endocrine and autonomic stress responses. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2009;10(6):397-409. DOI: 10.1038/nrn2647
234. Vicario A, Abellán A, Desfilis E, Medina L. Genetic identification of the central nucleus and other components of the central extended amygdala in chicken during development *Front Neuroanat*. 2014 Sep;8:90. [published correction appears in *Front Neuroanat*. 2021 May 19;15:671725]. DOI: 10.3389/fnana.2014.00090
235. Vicario A, Abellán A, Medina L. Embryonic Origin of the Islet1 and Pax6 Neurons of the Chicken Central Extended Amygdala Using Cell Migration Assays and Relation to Different Neuropeptide-Containing Cells. *Brain Behav Evol*. 2015;85(3):139-169. DOI: 10.1159/000381004
236. Vicario A, Mendoza E, Abellán A, Scharff C, Medina L. Genoarchitecture of the extended amygdala in zebra finch, and expression of FoxP2 in cell corridors of different genetic profile. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2017;222(1):481-514. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-016-1229-6
237. Waclaw RR, Ehrman LA, Pierani A, Campbell K. Developmental origin of the neuronal subtypes that comprise the amygdalar fear circuit in the mouse. *J Neurosci*. 2010;30(20):6944-6953. DOI: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.5772-09.2010
238. Wild JM. The ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus in the zebra finch (*Taeniopygia guttata*): Afferent and efferent projections in relation to the control of reproductive behavior. *J Comp Neurol*. 2017;525(12):2657-2676. DOI: 10.1002/cne.24225
239. Wullimann MF. The Neuromeric/Prosomeric Model in Teleost Fish Neurobiology. *Brain Behav Evol*. 2022. DOI:10.1159/000525607

240. Wullimann MF, Mueller T. Teleostean and mammalian forebrains contrasted: Evidence from genes to behavior [published correction appears in *J Comp Neurol*. 2004 Oct 25;478(4):427-8]. *J Comp Neurol*. 2004;475(2):143-162. DOI: 10.1002/cne.20183
241. Xie J, Kuenzel WJ, Anthony NB, Jurkevich A. Subpallial and hypothalamic areas activated following sexual and agonistic encounters in male chickens. *Physiol Behav*. 2010;101(3):344-359. DOI: 10.1016/j.physbeh.2010.06.004
242. Xie J, Kuenzel WJ, Sharp PJ, Jurkevich A. Appetitive and consummatory sexual and agonistic behaviour elicits FOS expression in aromatase and vasotocin neurones within the preoptic area and bed nucleus of the stria terminalis of male domestic chickens. *J Neuroendocrinol*. 2011;23(3):232-243. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2826.2011.02108.x
243. Xin Q, Ogura Y, Uno L, Matsushima T. Selective contribution of the telencephalic arcopallium to the social facilitation of foraging efforts in the domestic chick. *Eur J Neurosci*. 2017;45(3):365-380. DOI: 10.1111/ejn.13475
244. Xu Q, Tam M, Anderson SA. Fate mapping Nkx2.1-lineage cells in the mouse telencephalon. *J Comp Neurol*. 2008;506(1):16-29. DOI: 10.1002/cne.21529
245. Yamamoto K, Sun Z, Wang HB, Reiner A. Subpallial amygdala and nucleus taeniae in birds resemble extended amygdala and medial amygdala in mammals in their expression of markers of regional identity. *Brain Res Bull*. 2005 Sep 15;66(4-6):341-7. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainresbull.2005.02.016.
246. Ye J, Veinante P. Cell-type specific parallel circuits in the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis and the central nucleus of the amygdala of the mouse. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2019;224(3):1067-1095. DOI: 10.1007/s00429-018-01825-1
247. Yokoyama S, Altun A, DeNardo DF. Molecular convergence of infrared vision in snakes. *Mol Biol Evol*. 2011;28(1):45-48. DOI: 10.1093/molbev/msq267
248. Young LJ, Wang Z. The neurobiology of pair bonding. *Nat Neurosci*. 2004;7(10):1048-1054. DOI: 10.1038/nn1327

Figure Legends

Fig. 1. Schematic drawings of the chicken telencephalon (E18 embryo) at commissural (left) and postcommissural (right) levels. The central extended amygdala and its subdivisions are better appreciated at commissural level (pink area), while the medial extended amygdala is observed at postcommissural levels (blue area). Using a color code, the major neuron subtypes are represented, based on embryonic origin, transcription factor expression and neurotransmitter/neuropeptide content (for simplicity, not all subtypes are included; see text for additional details). Some of the connections of the homologous cells are known in mammals (see Table) and we make a proposal on the existence of similar connections in chicken (diagrams in squares at the bottom), which would need to be investigated. We also make predictions of preferential connections between neurons with identical embryonic origin and similar molecular profile. **Abbreviations:** ac, anterior commissure; ArP, arcopallium; BSTL, lateral bed nucleus of the stria terminalis; CeC, capsular central amygdala; Ceov, oval subnucleus of the central amygdala; lfb, lateral forebrain bundle; lv, lateral ventricle; Me, medial amygdala; NiP, nidopallium; Pa, pallidal embryonic division; PO, preoptic area; pINP, peri-intrapeduncular island field; Pov, perioval zone; Se, septum; SPVco, core part of the supraoptic-paraventricular hypothalamic division; St, striatum; Std, dorsal striatal embryonic division; Stv, ventral striatal embryonic division; TOH, telencephalon-opto-hypothalamic embryonic division; vaf, ventral amygdalofugal tract.

Table: Major neuron subtypes of the mouse extended amygdala based on embryonic origin and presence of similar cells in sauropsids

Part	Origen	Embryonic TF or SP	Main NT	NP*	Projections	Function	Main mouse subdivisions	Cells present in sauropsids**
Ce	Std	Pax6	GABA	ENK (PKCd)	Short (Ce+BSTL)	OFF in conditioned fear response	CeC, CeL	Yes: T, C, Z
	Stv	Islet1	GABA	CRF?	Short (BSTL) + long (LH, PAG, PB, DVC)	Anxiety	CeL, CeM	Yes: T, C (CRF only found in birds)
	Pa	Nkx2.1 Lhx6	GABA	SST	Short (Ce, BSTL) +long (PAG, PB)	ON in conditioned fear response	CeL, CeM	Yes: T, C, Z
Me	Pavc	Nkx2.1 Lhx6	GABA	SST	Long (POM, VMHvl, PMv)	Promote sexual behavior	MeA (mainly MeAD), MePD	Yes: T, C, Z
	PO	Shh Dbx1 Lhx5	GABA	NOS	Long (PVN/AH, VMHdm, PMd)	Promote agonistic behavior	MeA, MePV	Yes: L, T, C, Z
	TOH	Foxg1 Otp Lhx5	Glu	?	Short (BSTM) + long (AH? VMH? PM?)	Inhibit social behavior?	MeA (mainly MeAV), MePD (mainly medial half), MePV (core periphery)	Yes: L, T, C, Z

* Progenitors of each embryonic domain can produce more than one type of peptidergic neuron, but for simplicity in this table only selected cell subsets of peptidergic cells are included. ** Based on embryonic origin, TF/SP expression, and presence of NT/NP-specific containing cells.

Abbreviations: AH, anterior (alar) hypothalamus; BSTL, lateral bed nucleus of the stria terminalis; BSTM, medial bed nucleus of the stria terminalis; C, chicken; Ce, central amygdala; CeC, capsular Ce; CeL, lateral Ce; CeM, medial Ce; con, conditioned; CRF, corticotropin releasing factor; DVC, dorsal vagal complex; ENK, enkephalin; L, lizard; LH, lateral hypothalamus; Me, medial amygdala; MeA, anterior Me; MeAD, anterodorsal Me; MeAV, anteroventral Me; MePD, posterodorsal Me; MePV, posteroventral Me; NOS, nitric oxide synthase; NP, neuropeptide; NT, neurotransmitter; Pa, pallidal embryonic division; Pavc, ventrocaudal Pa (Diagonal); PMd, dorsal premammillary nucleus; PMv, ventral premammillary nucleus; PO, preoptic embryonic division; POM, medial preoptic nucleus; PVN, paraventricular hypothalamic nucleus; T, turtle; TF, transcription factor; TOH, telencephalon-opto-hypothalamic embryonic division; SP, signaling protein; SST, somatostatin; Std, dorsal striatal embryonic division; Stv, ventral striatal embryonic division; VMH, ventromedial hypothalamic nucleus; VMHdm, dorsomedial VMH; VMHvl, ventrolateral VMH; Z, zebra finch.

